

Integral Ecology in Pope Francis's *Laudato Si'*:
The Meaning of the Papal Category of Integral Ecology for the Haitian Context.

by

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Abstract

Haiti is facing an unprecedented ecological crisis today. This crisis appears at the level of climate change and by the loss of biodiversity among others. Many scientists and world religious leaders have started to respond more effectively to this pressing issue. Pope Francis raises his voice in an impactful way, inviting everyone to ecological conversion and to frankly dialogue about caring for our common home and protecting the planet. Beginning with the “The Legend of the Hummingbird” this paper frames the project into its eco-theological and ministerial context. This legend teaches in a poetic way the lesson of the consequences of remaining inactive in the face of the alarming situation happening to our common and shared home. We all are part of God’s creation, called to be in just and loving relationship while becoming more present to ourselves and the human and more-than-human neighbors with whom we are deeply connected.

Dedication

To all those who belong to my blood and spiritual-religious family and to the Earth Community at large. To all those who are striving to “heal the world (including the little black country of Haiti) and make it a better place.” To all those who are caring for one another (particularly for the most vulnerable ones – the minority groups) and to our common and shared home (i.e., our suffering sister Mother Earth).

Acknowledgement¹

The Environment...

The hour has arrived for us to act.
You and I, we are **both** concerned.
Our **e**nvironment is threatened.
We long to save it, and not see ourselves perish.

As **con**scious beings,
We must make life **liv**able in our world
Obey**i**ng its natural laws and principles
Will **br**ing forth a better life.

Our responsibility grows greater and greater,
And our answers less useful, changing day by day.
Oh **m**y God, what then should we all do?

Face**d** with this alarming situation,
Should **not** we see ourselves as one single family
Striving for a world that is our only consolation?

¹ The research project was written during Haiti's time of trials, and **this poetry *The Environment...* is to acknowledge and say thank you in an anonymous manner to all those who make this work possible and who contribute to improve its quality with their insightful feedbacks, comments and suggestions.** The original French version which is a sonnet and an acrostic poem was first of all dedicated to our suffering sister Mother Earth (our common home) on June 5th, 2012 – The World Environment Day, some days the before the UN Conference on Sustainable Development or Rio + 20 (20-22 June 2012). See: Jean Bertin ST LOUIS. "The Environment...", In: <https://festivalforpoetry.com/2022/04/06/poetry-reading-the-environment-by-jean-bertin-st-louis/> accessed august 21st, 2022.

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INTRODUCTION

This research Project analyzes Pope Francis' understanding of "integral ecology" in *Laudato Si'* and considers its reception and implications for Haiti. In writing this thesis, I have been inspired in many ways by the Legend of the Hummingbird, made popular by the French agroecologist Pierre Rabhi:

One day, a long time ago and in a faraway place, **there was a huge forest fire** raging in the countryside. **All the animals were terrified**, running around in circles, screaming, crying and helplessly watching the impending disaster. But **there**, in the middle of the flames, and above the cowering animals, **a tiny hummingbird was busy flying from a small pond to the fire**, each time fetching a few drops with its beak to throw on the flames. The hummingbird kept doing this again and again. After a while, **an old grouchy armadillo**, annoyed by this ridiculous and useless agitation on the part of the hummingbird, cried out: "Tiny bird! Don't be a fool. Those tiny drops of water will never put out the fire and save us all!" To which the hummingbird replied, "I know that, but I'm going to do my part."²

Like the hummingbird, I know that I cannot fix the environmental crisis on my own, and that whatever contribution I can make is very small compared to the scale and urgency of the challenges we face. Still, as a researcher in the field of eco-theology and eco-spirituality, as a Jesuit poet and priest, and as a native Haitian, I have decided to do my part. I have had privileged access to a wealth of knowledge and reflection, which I want to bring to bear on the problems of my country, with the humble desire to be of service. The legend of the hummingbird also points to our interconnectedness, and invites us to collective action; in that light, I am ready to bring my experience as a leader in the Haitian Church into dialogue with scholars and other actors who are

² Un jour, dit la légende, il y eut un immense incendie de forêt. Tous les animaux terrifiés, atterrés, observaient impuissants le désastre. Seul le petit colibri s'activait, allant chercher quelques gouttes avec son bec pour les jeter sur le feu. Après un moment, le tatou, agacé par cette agitation dérisoire, lui dit : « Colibri ! Tu n'es pas fou ? Ce n'est pas avec ces gouttes d'eau que tu vas éteindre le feu ! ». Et le colibri lui répondit : « Je le sais, mais je fais ma part. See: <http://www.seveilleretsepanouirdemaniereraisonnee.com/2016/06/parlons-ecologie-avec-les-enfants-la-legende-du-colibri-de-denis-kormann.html> (accessed August 12th, 2022).

reflecting on issues that affect the whole world, so that we can mutually enrich each other's efforts in this regard.

To this end, I will focus on Pope Francis' papal encyclical, *Laudato Si'* (*LS*), published in 2015. This document from the Magisterium of the Roman Catholic Church is in continuity with the Catholic Social Teaching, but also makes original contributions in light of the contemporary context. One original aspect, which is fully appropriate to the thematic context of our shared environmental crisis, is that the encyclical is not addressed only to an audience within the Roman Church, or even to "all people of good will," but rather to "everyone on the planet."³

As far as its content is concerned, *LS* places great emphasis on the concept of "integral ecology," which is about seeing how different components and dimensions of the world are interrelated. The theme of integral ecology, which has long been defined as the core of the scientific principle according to which "everything is interconnected" (Integral Theory), has come to be an important topic for public debate, and the Catholic Church has increasingly played a role in those debates.⁴ This is part of the prophetic mission of the Church. Moreover, Pope Francis insists on the importance of integral ecology as something which needs to be taken seriously by all Christians. "Living our vocation to be protectors or stewards of God's handiwork [i.e., heaven and earth] is essential to a life of virtue; it is not an optional or a secondary aspect of

³ Pope Francis. Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si': On the Care for Our Common Home* (Vatican City: Vatican Press, 2015), n. 3. Hereafter this Church document is cited as *LS*. Also see the respective audiences (or subjects of dialogue) of the following Encyclical Letters: *Pacem in Terris* of Saint John Paul II (addressed to all people of good will) and *Laudato Si'* of Pope Francis (addressed to everyone living/residing on the planet Earth).

⁴ It is important to see how the level of consciousness and/or awareness as well as the degree of recognition of the Roman Catholic Church are now refined. Almost every important meeting or Summit among the leaders of the world on matters related to ecology (i.e., to the earth, our common home) today is informed by the position of the Roman Catholic Church, position that has been taken in preparation to that meeting or Summit. That was the case with the papal Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si'*. See also the link of the last summit of the world leaders convened by the new President of the USA last April in order to enhance Trump's environmental politics: https://www.state.gov/leaders-summit-on-climate/schedule/?fbclid=IwAR0aYjAcSSzgdEvh6w7KgRryVibaClOVGrD623p6-6ak8A_HMe9sYJwljh4 (accessed May 31st, 2020).

our Christian experience.”⁵ The present research project offers an exposition of integral ecology, considering it the main theme of Pope Francis’s encyclical letter *Laudato Si’*, in ways that could be helpful for those who are interested in Haiti’s overall ecological system (both at the social and environmental levels). It is not an assessment or a critical appraisal of Haiti’s multiple interconnected social and environmental crises but a way of approaching ecology through existing relationships of harmony and/or disharmony between created entities. Rather than providing an exhaustive evaluation of Haiti’s reality, here I have only strived to respond to the simple question: Why is integral ecology a helpful concept for addressing the Haitian situation?

In Chapter 1, I present the concept of integral ecology as discussed by Pope Francis in *Laudato Si’*, unpacking its meaning in dialogue with the wider scope of the encyclical. In Chapter 2, I argue that integral ecology is extremely relevant to Haiti, not only because of the country’s environmental crisis, but especially because, by helping us see how it is interconnected with the country’s other layered challenges, puts that crisis into perspective. In Chapter 3, I show how some Haitian Church actors are applying the Pope’s call to spread awareness and work towards integral ecology in practice. In the Conclusion, I summarize key insights, add some final reflections, and suggest avenues for future research, reflection, and action.

⁵ Cf. *LS* 217. As Catholic environmental ethicist Joshtröm Kureethadam says in his article *Ecological Virtues*, “there is a growing awareness of the importance of the role of ecological virtues [such as praise, gratitude, care, justice, work, sobriety, humility] for the care of our common planetary home in the context of the contemporary ecological crisis.” Joshtröm Isaac Kureethadam. “Ecological Virtues in *Laudato Si’*”. *Ethics in Progress*. Vol. 7 (2016). No. 1, Art. #5, 44-66. In her article *In Defense of Resilience as an Ecological Virtue*, published in December 2020, Agnes Brazal insists that resilience to be considered as one of the ecological virtues, “Resilience as the ability to bounce back and adapt better is a goal not only for the individual but the community and its structures as well.” In: <https://catholicethics.com/forum/in-defense-of-resilience-as-an-ecological-virtue/> accessed august 12th, 2022.

CHAPTER ONE: Presentation of *Laudato Si'* and Integral Ecology

This chapter introduces the general context of the Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si'* and the papal appropriation of the theme of “integral ecology.” The premise is that humanity’s relationship with the rest of creation is one of union and interdependence.⁶ This chapter, then, will first explore the basic principle found in *Laudato Si'*, that *everything is interconnected* in God’s creation, and especially the ways in which some realities are interconnected between themselves and mutually dependent on one another. Secondly, this chapter will show how Integral Ecology is *also* capable of leading to a *way of dialogue* or a common ground for mutual understanding, appreciation, and respect between all Haitians. Thirdly, this chapter will establish the relationships that exist between dialogue, the common good, solidarity and the dignity of all Haitians, while illustrating these relationships with examples.

1.1 General context of Laudato Si' and Integral Ecology: Pope Francis prays:

“Teach us [our Father, our Lord and our God] to discover the worth of each thing, to be filled with awe and contemplation, to recognize that we are profoundly united with every creature as we journey towards your infinite light.”⁷ Pope Francis wrote *Laudato Si' (Praise be to you)* in 2015, the same year of the adoption of the Paris Agreement. This was his second Encyclical

⁶ LS 12: “if we feel intimately united with all that exists, then sobriety and care will well up spontaneously.” The result of intimacy with the rest of creation will be twofold: there is interconnectedness in creation (this act of love of the Father) and in redemption or salvation (this act of love of the Son). This point is articulated also by Fabien Revol: “La création actuelle en tant que création continue et la rédemption en tant que création originelle continuée sont alors une seule et même chose. [...] Cosmologie et sotériologie se rejoignent. Ainsi, si dans l’actualité création (cosmologie) et rédemption (sotériologie) se rejoignent, cela veut dire non seulement que la création originelle s’y actualise mais que la nouvelle création s’y anticipe. » (“Current creation as continued creation and redemption as original continued creation are then one and the same. [...] Cosmology and soteriology come together. Thus, if in actuality creation (cosmology) and redemption (soteriology) come together, this means not only that the original creation is actualized there but that the new creation is anticipated there”). Fabien Revol, *Le temps de la création* (Paris: Les Éditions Du Cerf, 2015), 90-91.

⁷ LS 246.

Letter, composed two years after *Lumen Fidei* (*The light of faith*, published in the same year of his ascent to the papacy). In 2020, he authored his third Encyclical Letter, *Fratelli Tutti* (*We are all brothers*), as well as his Apostolic Exhortation, “Querida Amazonia”.

The Pontiff signed the final draft of *Laudato Si'* on May 24th, 2015, in honor of *Mary, Help of Christians*⁸ some days before the official publication in June. The Pontiff also seems to have had in mind the COP21, which was the important United Nations conference on Climate Change that led to the 2016 Paris Agreement. The Papal Encyclical Letter invites each person on the planet, but most particularly the world leaders and policy makers, to reflect in preparation for the upcoming summit on the destruction of the planet by anthropogenic climate change with the following warning. “If present trends continue, *this* century may well witness extraordinary climate change and an unprecedented destruction of ecosystems, with serious consequences for all of us.”⁹

In his encyclical Pope Francis engages the North American ecological historian, Lynn White Jr., who has said that “[s]ince the roots of our trouble are largely religious [since it is originated in our interpretation of the meaning of the biblical verse of Genesis 13: 13 *having dominion over creation*], the remedy must be religious as well. We must re-think and re-feel our nature and destiny.”¹⁰ Because the climate is not only a “common resource” but a “common

⁸ This advocacy of the Virgin is not to be confused with *Mary, Our Lady of Perpetual Help*, which is the Patroness of Haiti, my dear country, celebrated on June 27th.

⁹ LS 24. The italic is mine, and I want to stress that the twenty first century in which we are living today (and not the next one), according to the Pope, is threatened of climate change related destruction, one of the many aspects of the crisis we are going through.

¹⁰ Lynn White Jr., “The Historical Roots of Our Ecologic Crisis.” *Science* 3/1967, Volume 155, Issue 3767, (1203 – 1207), 1207. See also: Preston Bristow. “The Root of our Ecological Crisis”. *Journal of Creation*, volume 15, no. 1 (April 2001): 76-79.

good,”¹¹ a source of life, the Pope considers an ecclesial point of view of great help for changing the debate on major environmental changes that affect the climate, water sources and biodiversity. This is a key contribution of the Roman Catholic Church in the discussion on climate change.

1.2 Climate controversy within and outside of the Church: The failure to acknowledge the reality of climate change, let alone take responsibility for it, by many actors both within and outside the Church, represents a multifaceted challenge. This is particularly true among the leaders of the industrialized nations. Yet, the Pope warns that “Climate change is a global problem with grave implications: environmental, social, economic, political and for the distribution of goods both equally and equitably. It represents one of the principal challenges facing humanity in our day. Its worst impact will probably be felt [most] by developing countries in coming decades.”¹²

What should we do with respect to how climate change affects us emotionally? Terms such as eco-fear, eco-anxiety, and eco-despair are now common parlance and may explain the resistance to embrace climate science.¹³ Many people also resist making simple changes in their

¹¹ LS 23: “The climate is a common good, belonging to all and meant for all. At the global level, it is a complex system linked to many of the essential conditions for human life.”

¹² LS 25. Climate change, for many, appears to be a set of cumulative events in which each single event must be taken into account in a very particular way and with a very particular attention. In the midst of the tension between economy and ecology, the concept “green job” is a brilliant invention that shows how audible, how good and how optimistic is the marriage between the two conflicting terms. This is quite similar with what happens with the concept of environmental innovation (including that of the circular economy). See: Prieto-Sandoval, Vanessa, Carmen Jaca, and Marta Ormazabal. “Towards a Consensus on the Circular Economy.” *Journal of cleaner production* 179 (2018): 605–615.

¹³ Christine Perakslis defines eco-anxiety as “a chronic fear of environmental doom, usually based on feelings of powerlessness about environmental change or climate change. Other associated terms include: eco-fear, eco-despair, eco-grief, eco-distress, and eco-angst.” Christine Perakslis, “Uncertainty Tolerance (UT): Recycling Eco-Anxiety into Eco-Empowerment [Last Word].” *IEEE technology & society magazine* 39, no. 2 (2020): 80-80.

daily routines, such as implementing the 3 R's (reduce, reuse, and recycle), which would help reduce their carbon footprint. As a result, the goal of limiting global greenhouse gas-emissions so as to keep warming to 1.5 Celsius degree above pre-industrial levels has been extremely challenging, and there are serious doubts about whether we can reach net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050.¹⁴

Meanwhile, climate change is just one issue among other equally urgent ones affecting the planet, such as biodiversity loss. Biodiversity means all forms of life that pertain to the fauna, the flora and much more. Although the word biodiversity does not exist as such in the Holy Scriptures, the concept is deeply biblical and rooted in the creation narratives (Priestly in Genesis 1 and Jahwist in Genesis 2 and 3). Some authors, such as Lynn White, have shown how these narratives have been misused to justify the abuse and exploitation of nature, and how a renewed understanding of them is necessary.¹⁵

Because the challenge is both urgent and complex, an integral, multidisciplinary approach is necessary. Indeed, theologians Lane Dermot and Sean McDonagh insist that according to *Laudato Si'*, theology – the science of God *seen as omnipresent in all that exists* – and ecology – the science of the community *understood as ecosystem and/or biodiversity in*

¹⁴ LS 26. Aware of the issue, Pope Francis argue that, “There is an urgent need to develop policies so that, in the next few years, the emission of carbon dioxide and other highly polluting gases can be drastically reduced, for example, substituting for fossil fuels and developing sources of renewable energy”.

¹⁵ For whatever reason, Christians have often tried to combine and harmonize these two creation stories, usually by seeing the Eden story [of the Yahwist account] as an elaboration of what God does on the sixth day of the Priestly account. When the two stories are combined, many Christians have picked parts of the message from each story, and lost the important constraints. The freedom of the Yahwistic story is mingled with the authority of the Priestly account, but the constraints of either story are lost. The unrestrained freedom and authority that come from misreading these two stories is what people (such as Lynn White) point to when they say that Christianity encourages the abuse and exploitation of nature. See: “Preaching on Genesis 1. Comparing the Two Creation Stories in Genesis”, In: <http://www.eco-justice.org/gen1a.asp> (accessed May 25th, 2022). See also White Jr., “The Historical Roots of Our Ecologic Crisis.”, 1205. Referring to the Book of Scripture, White is convinced that, “by destroying pagan animism, Christianity made it possible to exploit nature in a mood of indifference to the feelings of natural objects.”

which everything is put together in the name of God – are capable of dialoguing, that is, journeying together in a reciprocally enriching way:

Laudato Si' is making a clear case for a two-way conversation between ecology and theology. Ecology will challenge theology to move into a more integrated paradigm [not remaining attached to the sole and unidirectional logic of *black and white*], to explain the meaning of dominion in Genesis 1, and to foster a new praxis dedicated to the healing of the planet. Equally, theology will challenge ecology to move from an anthropocentric approach to a theocentric approach [an approach in which God can be simultaneously *within, outside, above and beyond* all that exist], to make way for the cultivation of beauty in our world, and to give priority to hearing the cry of the poor and the earth.¹⁶

Furthermore, we must remember that ecology itself is about both natural sciences and social sciences, all very well-integrated within the realm of what has been called life sciences. Framing it this way allows us to see with even more clarity how theology can contribute to the dialogue:

All human endeavor — from food production and resource use to economics, politics, and education — needs to be [integrally] ecologized, in the sense that implications for the fate of the entire Earth community need to be considered. Conversely, ecology needs to draw from the whole spectrum of human inquiry, not only from the natural sciences, but [also] from the human and social sciences, from the world's spiritual traditions (Eastern, Western, and indigenous), and from collective wisdom and individual insights.¹⁷

This dialogue on the level of reflection and analysis must go together with collaboration on the level of praxis. If we want to overcome the environmental crisis, we need to act both individually and communally. As the Legend of the Hummingbird suggests, even the smallest individual action can help create awareness and perhaps inspire other actors to do their part. The leadership shown by children and youth on environmental advocacy is a further reason to believe in the possibility of real change.¹⁸ Recognizing the profound desire to save the planet by so many

¹⁶ Dermot A. Lane and Seán McDonagh. *Theology and Ecology in Dialogue: The Wisdom of Laudato Si'* (New York / Mahwah, NJ: Paulist Press, 2021), 22.

¹⁷ Sam Mickey, Sean M. Kelly and Adam Robbert, *The Variety of Integral Ecologies: Nature, Culture, and Knowledge in the Planetary Era*. (New York: SUNY Press, 2017), 189.

¹⁸ See Earth Charter International, <https://earthcharter.org/library/the-earth-charter-booklet/> (accessed July 25th, 2022).

committed world citizens, Pope Francis is hopeful in the face of the challenges: “Yet all is not lost. Human beings while capable of the worst [the destruction of the climate, then that of the planet], are also capable of rising above themselves, choosing again what is good, and making a new start.”¹⁹

1.3 Integral ecology and other correlated themes, proverbs or sayings: The papal category of “integral ecology” is mentioned at least ten times in *Laudato Si'*; the term is shorthand for the principle that “everything is (inter-)connected.”²⁰ As scholars have noted, Pope Francis’ use and understanding of the term is influenced by various currents of thought “which highlighted both the complexity and integrity of the world.”²¹ To unpack this concept, then, it is

¹⁹ LS 205. As in the Legend of the Hummingbird’s implication that each species in the forest has a specific role to play, Father Godefroy Midy argues that this collective effort implies the necessary complementarity of inter and transdisciplinarity. “Chaque discipline aura à la fois son objectif, son charisme, son autonomie, sa méthodologie, avec la capacité de mettre les fruits de ses investigations au service des autres savoirs, et recevant d’eux ; interdisciplinarité et complémentarité. Forts de leur partage et enrichissement mutuels, tous les savoirs se dirigeront vers cette métadiscipline qu’est le grand projet commun de répondre au cri de la terre menacée : il s’agit de sauver la vie [Each discipline will have at the same time its objective, its charisma, its autonomy, its methodology, with the capacity to put the fruits of its investigations at the service of other knowledge, and receiving from them; interdisciplinarity and complementarity. Strengthened by their sharing and mutual enrichment, all knowledge will be directed towards this metadiscipline which is the great common project of responding to the cry of the threatened earth: it is a question of saving life]. Godefroy Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise. Une lecture spirituelle ignacienne de la réalité actuelle (d’Haïti)* (Port-au-Prince: Centre de Recherche, de Réflexion, de Formation et d’Action Sociale-CERFAS, 2014), 79. Hereafter this book will be cited as : Godefroy Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise*.

²⁰ See: LS 70, 92, 111, 138, 240 (excerpts on connection and interconnection). See also: Pope Francis. Encyclical Letter *Fratelli Tutti: On Fraternity and Social Friendship* (Vatican City: Vatican Press, 2020), n. 34. See further: LS 92, 120, 137, 138, 142 (excerpts on relation and interrelation) and also LS 143 (excerpt on dialogue). Note that, according to Mary Evelyn Tucker, John Grim and Andrew Angyal, Thomas Berry has used the papal category of “integral ecology” in 1995 and he has great influence on Pope Francis’s work particularly his appropriation of the same concept. The same thing happens with Leonardo Boff’s concept of “holistic ecology” Mary Evelyn Tucker et al., *Thomas Berry: An Autobiography*. (New York: Columbia University Press, 2019), 147.

²¹ “Trends and scientific concepts representative of this approach include, among others, *holism* which was formulated in the 20-ties of the twentieth century by Jan Ch. Smuts, the *General Systems Theory* initiated in the 30-ties by Ludwig von Bertalanffy and the *integral theory* introduced by Ken Wilber in the 70-ties of the previous century. It seems that among the twentieth-century concepts of holistic and integral approach to the reality, the greatest influence on the thought of the Pope had the earlier versions of *integral ecology* which many scholars connected with Wilber’s integral theory. Scientific literature usually refers to three versions of integral ecology, namely, the concept proposed by Ken Wilber which was developed by the followers of his thought, Sean Esbjörn-Hargens and Michael Zimmerman, the concept proposed by a liberation theologian Leonardo Boff and the concept of Thomas Berry, a cultural historian.” See: Fr. Ryszard F. Sadowski SDB. “Inspirations of Pope Francis’ Concept of Integral Ecology” *Seminare* (Institute of Ecology and Bioethics), vol. 37, 2016, no. 4, 70.

useful to explore correlated themes that have to do with (inter-)connection and (inter)connectedness. For example, themes like relation, dialogue, (inter-)dependency, exchange, interaction, harmony between individuals (or social groups) among themselves as well as between individuals and their environment. Thinking about integral ecology is thinking about the relationship that exists between the Creator God and all that is. It is thinking about God as both Father and Mother of everything in creation, including the daughters and sons that are present in creation as members of the Earth community.

In the Haitian context, the theme of interconnectedness that underlies the concept of integral ecology can be found in several popular proverbs and sayings. For example, the Creole language spoken in Haiti, has an analogy for interconnection in the following saying, *yon sèl nou fèb, ansanm nou fò* [alone we are weak, together we are strong]. This indeed means *youn bezwen lòt yon fason pou tout sistèm nan fonksyone byen* [each component of the entire system needs the others in order for the whole system to function well]. Similarly, *tout bagay ki egziste nan kreyasyon Bondye a yo makonnen ansanm yon fason si youn ladan yo ta pran kou se lòt la ki va santi doulè a otomatikman* [everything that exists in God's creation is interconnected in such a way that if one is hurt, the other will immediately feel the pain]. This idea is powerfully expressed in the Haitian proverb, *nen pran kou, je kouri dlo* [when the nose is hit, the eyes shed tears]. Another saying that reinforces the theme of solidarity and mutual belonging is *maladi yon fanm se pou tout fanm* [a woman's sickness is the sickness of all women].

These proverbs illustrate the community-oriented mindset of Haitian culture, where interconnectedness not only emerges during celebrations of important life events such as marriage, the birth of a child, or graduation, but also in times of hardship. Our experience of earthquakes is a vivid example. For Haitian people (following Newell J. Philipp)

interconnectedness is not just an essential feature of life but of created reality.²² Our human soul, body, and spirit are all interconnected. Our freedom, our memory, our intelligence, and our will – as found in the Ignatian *Suscipe* Prayer of the *Spiritual Exercises*²³ – are all interconnected. The mineral, vegetal, and animal worlds that are present both within and beyond us are all interconnected. Everything around us in the world – from the birds migrating from tree to tree, to the fishes of the deep sea and of the coral reefs – is interconnected. Ultimately, even “the divine and the human are one [...] They are conjoined. Heaven is to be found in the things of earth. The divine is to be cherished within the earthliness of human life and relationship.”²⁴ All that exists on Earth is interconnected. As we would say in Haitian Creole, *yo tout yo makonnen ansanm* [they are all coupled/connected together]. This idea of interconnectedness or *yo tout yo makonnen ansanm* can be summarized by the concept of integral ecology as it is found in various parts of *Laudato Si*’.

In the Haitian context and that of many other non-Western countries in the world, “integral ecology” first implies *the need for multi-leveled approach*. All of us, from our diverse backgrounds and positionalities, are invited to creatively address the ecological crisis. Secondly, *the capacity of being set free from all economic or political pressure and tendencies* is of crucial importance. In the context of power dynamics in Haiti, being set free from the elites of the socio-

²² Newell J. Philip describes something similar in the Celtic spiritual tradition. Newell J. Philip, *Sacred Earth, Sacred Soul: Celtic Wisdom for Reawakening to What Our Souls Know and Healing the World* (New York, NY: Harper Collins Publishers, 2021), xx.

²³ The *Spiritual Exercises* (SE) of Saint Ignatius # 234. See: Ignatius, and George E. Ganss. *Ignatius of Loyola: the Spiritual Exercises and Selected Works* (New York: Paulist Press, 1991). Hereafter, this work will be cited as: Saint Ignatius. *Spiritual Exercises*.

²⁴ This is part of the vision of Irenaeus of Lyons (ca. 140-202), one of the most eminent authors of the Celtic wisdom, according to the author. See: Newell J. Philip. *Sacred Earth, Sacred Soul*, 23.

economic and political structure is a great challenge. Thirdly, we need to cultivate *the new, integral, and inter-disciplinary capabilities for handling different aspects of the crisis.*²⁵

As a world community, we must move toward an approach that is conducive to changing the world while simultaneously changing us and making us more human. The response to the question “What makes us truly human?” must be answered contextually – in both time and location – since yesterday’s response to the same question might greatly differ from today’s response. A Haitian approach to integral ecology – which emphasizes the link between the social and environmental dimensions, should include both ordinary people and researchers from different backgrounds or fields of study. Here, I aim to contribute to that collective and ongoing effort through an approach to integral ecology that takes into account its relationship to other fields of knowledge and wisdom, such as theology (that of creation in particular), comparative religions, cosmogenesis, and wisdom of the earth or ecosophy – understood as the “philosophy of ecological harmony/equilibrium,” as defined by the deep ecologist Arne Naess.²⁶

1.4. Integral ecology and the fundamental relationships: Pope Francis’s notion of integral ecology can be described as a qualified anthropocentrism, as opposed to biocentrism. In other words, the human person, whose dignity is at the core of Catholic Social Teaching, is still the main point of reference, even as non-human beings are more fully recognized in *LS* than in most earlier encyclicals. From the perspective of human subjectivity, Pope Francis describes integral ecology in terms of four fundamental relationships, namely, one’s relationship *with God*,

²⁵ Here, I refer to what Lane Dermot has borrowed from paragraphs 135, 183, 197 of *Laudato Si’*. See: Lane Dermot A. et al.. *Theology and Ecology in Dialogue*, 23.

²⁶ Arne Naess. “The Shallow and The Deep, Long-range Ecology Movements. A Summary.” Sessions George (ed.). *Deep Ecology for the 21st Century* (Boston: Random House, 1994), 115.

with the world, with the rest of humanity, and with oneself. The interaction between the four seems to be drawn from Thomas Aquinas’s approach to charity as the first among the theological virtues.²⁷ Integral ecology is founded on their respective interaction or interconnectedness²⁸ especially with reference to the *sine qua non* condition for the validity of the principle according to which in the world “everything is related”²⁹ and “everything is interrelated”³⁰ or “everything is connected”³¹ and “everything is interconnected.”³²

A related way of understanding these relationships in the encyclical is through the traditional “God-Humanity-World” triangle, in which the latter two categories have intrinsic value, understood in terms of dignity (especially in the case of human persons) or worth (in the case of created things in general), by virtue of being created and loved by the former. In this view, humans are called to live in harmony with God and the rest of Creation, but they are also capable of disrupting the balance. Indeed, human-caused climate change and other forms of environmental destruction causes the world to be out of balance and is therefore a grave sin; a sin for which the affluent minority of the world’s population bears disproportionate responsibility. In order to recover the balance in these relationships, Pope Francis calls for a process of

²⁷ See: Aquinas. *Summa Theologiae*, Second Part of the Second Part, Question 23, article 6 (Vol. I). Translated by The Fathers of the English Dominican Province (New York: Benziger Brothers Inc., 1947). See also: Cardinal Reinhard Marx “Everything is connected”: On the Relevance of an Integral Understanding of Reality in *Laudato Si’*. Theological Studies 2016, Vol. 77(2), (2016), 295–307. According to Cardinal Marx, Pope Francis takes his place within the tradition of Catholic social doctrine, which was always aware of its obligation to an empirical realism, rooted in Aristotelian thinking and taken up by Thomas Aquinas.

²⁸ According to Archbishop Bernardito Auza, integral ecology is in fact “a paradigm able to articulate the fundamental multidimensionality of our relationships: our relationships with one another, our relationship with God, and our relationship with creation as a whole” Archbishop Bernardito Auza. “An Overview from the Point of View Pope Francis.” *The Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, Issue 64 (2016), 20.

²⁹ LS 92.

³⁰ LS 120.

³¹ LS 16, 91 and 117.

³² LS 70, 138, 240.

reconciliation that starts with cultivating the spiritual sensibility required to notice the deep connections: “An integral ecology includes taking time to recover a serene harmony with *creation* [the world], reflecting on *our lifestyle* and *our ideals* [humanity: ourselves and others], and contemplating the *Creator* who lives among us and surrounds us [God], whose presence ‘must not be contrived but found, uncovered.’”³³

Yet another way of describing these relationships is in the form of the Creator-Creation binary, in which the human self is grouped with other humans and non-humans, in order to emphasize the distinct nature of our relationship with God. This does not erase relationships among creatures, but it does reconfigure them by placing human beings at the heart of Creation, and by defining all other relations as a function of the principal relationship with our Creator. On behalf of Creation, we humble ourselves before God, who has given us power and dominion over the rest of the world. In Pope Francis’ understanding, this means that we have a responsibility to love and care for creation. Power and dominion is not synonymous with putting humanity either *at the center* or *above* creation in an exploitative or dominating way, but rather, humanity is a servant or steward for the rest of God’s handiwork. The four relationships are thus assimilated into an overarching whole, in a way that invites us to cultivate the *ecosophical* wisdom of integral ecology.³⁴ In the pope’s view, Saint Francis of Assisi³⁵ is a key reference who can

³³ *LS 225*, emphasis in original text. The expression “integral ecology” has been used ten times in Pope Francis’ encyclical, and it has the entire chapter four dedicated to it. Sánchez Sorondo and Veerabhadran Ramanathan see integral ecology from a totally horizontal point of view, arguing that, “The bond between humans and the natural world means that we live in an ‘integral ecology,’ and as such, an integrated approach to environmental and social justice is required.” The transcendental God is missing (without being absent), just as the immanent God is *in* the natural world through his presence and action/intervention. Marcelo Sánchez Sorondo and Veerabhadran Ramanathan. “Pursuit of integral ecology”. *Science*. Volume 352. Issue 6287 (2016), 747-748.

³⁴ This theme ecosophy (or wisdom of the earth), which is borrowed from Raimond Panikkar’s thought, has been further developed by Juan Carlos Valverde Campos in his recent book *Sortir de la crise écologique* (Le Coudray-Macouard : Saint-Léger éditions, 2018). See also: Maffesoli Michel. *Écosophie: Une écologie pour notre temps* (Paris: Editions du Cerf, 2017).

inspire people around the world to embrace an ecological wisdom which is ultimately theocentric, as it is rooted in God's love for all of Creation:

Saint Francis is the example par excellence of care for the vulnerable and of an integral ecology lived out joyfully and authentically. He is the patron saint of all who study and work in the area of ecology, and he is also much loved by non-Christians. He was particularly concerned for God's creation and for the poor and outcast. He loved, and was deeply loved for his joy, his generous self-giving, his openheartedness. He was a mystic and a pilgrim who lived in simplicity and in wonderful harmony *with God, with others, with nature* and *with himself* [that is, all the four requirements or conditions for an ecology to be integral]. He shows us just how inseparable the bond is between concern for nature, justice for the poor, commitment to society, and interior peace.³⁶

As Pope Francis shows, rootedness in a relationship with our Creator flows into humble and joyful solidarity with the rest of Creation, and vice versa. Indeed, God is discernably present in the world, just as the otherness of the immanent world opens us to transcendent alterity. The key to these dimensions is that God, who is love, self-communicates through creation:

By the word of the Lord the heavens were made' (Ps 33:6). This tells us that the world came about as the result of a decision, not from chaos or chance, and this exalts it all the more. The creating word expresses a free choice. The universe did not emerge as the result of arbitrary omnipotence, a show of force or a desire for self-assertion. *Creation is of the order of love*. God's love is the fundamental moving force in all created things: 'For you love all things that exist and detest none of the things that you have made; for you would not have made anything if you had hated it' (Wis 11:24). Every creature is thus the object of the Father's tenderness, who gives it its place in the world. Even the fleeting life of the least of beings is the object of his love, and in its few seconds of existence, God enfolds it with his affection. Saint Basil the Great described the Creator as 'goodness without measure' while Dante Alighieri spoke of 'the love which moves the sun and the stars.' Consequently, we can ascend from created things 'to the greatness of God and to his loving mercy.'³⁷

³⁵ See: *Canticle of the Creatures*, in *Francis of Assisi: Early Documents* (New York-London-Manila: 1999), 113-114, quoted in *LS* 87.

³⁶ *LS* 10, the emphasis on the four elements has been added.

³⁷ *LS* 77. Thanks be to love (or to the loving God) all we are interconnected. I want to recall here my poem on the self-sufficiency of love (or the loving God) through the following words, "A reality can be self-sufficient only if it transcends its own conditions of existence and life. Nothing is sufficient in itself and for itself. Love alone is enough for love at least. A reality can be self-sufficient only if it transcends time and space. Nothing is sufficient in itself and for itself. Love alone is enough for love at least." The translation is mine (Jean Bertin ST LOUIS. "Rien ne suffit en soi et par soi". *Anthologie Au Bonheur D'écrire*. Bordeaux: Les Dossiers D'Aquitaine, 2013, 12: "Une

Thus, the four relationships themselves are interconnected, even in their distinctiveness, and improving any of these relationships authentically helps us to improve all of them. Rather than expecting God to intervene in human affairs through extraordinary miracles, we would do well to learn to contemplate otherness in its multiple forms, starting with “the little ones” of the Gospels (Mt 18: 10; Mk 9: 42; Lk 17:2) those who are oppressed, such as indigenous peoples. God speaks to us through their faces, calling us to recognition and restoration of right relationship.

For Pope Francis, then, integral ecology refers to levels of fraternity/sorority in the midst of creation, since in the universe, “Everything is related, and we human beings are united as brothers and sisters on a wonderful pilgrimage, woven together by the love God has for each of his creatures and which also unites us in fond affection with brother sun, sister moon, brother river and mother earth.”³⁸ It is key to understand that God, Our Lord, is the One who through his love bonds us all together as brothers and sisters and as members of the Earth community (our living context); outside of Him, we are scattered and divided.

Pope Francis argues that integral ecology demands that we should continue to invest in scientific research that would give us a better understanding of the interconnections between the creatures that together make up ecosystems. This is the case, however, not only for pragmatic reasons, but also because of the intrinsic worth of all creatures and ecosystems.³⁹ More urgently,

réalité ne peut se suffire à elle-même que si elle transcende ses conditions propres d'existence et de vie. Rien ne suffit en soi et pour soi. L'amour seul suffit à l'amour tout au moins. Une réalité ne peut se suffire à elle-même que si elle transcende le temps et l'espace. Rien ne suffit en soi et pour soi. L'amour seul suffit à l'amour tout au moins.”)

³⁸ LS 94.

³⁹ LS 140. This also has to do with Thomas Berry's idea of a cosmology of cosmogenesis in which the Earth community depends on the greater structure of the universe. See also: Thomas Berry. *The Great Work: Our Way into the Future* (New York: Bell Tower, 1999), 26: “We now live not so much in a cosmos as in a cosmogenesis; that is, a universe ever coming into being through an irreversible sequence of transformations moving, in the larger arc of its development, from a lesser to a great order of complexity and from a lesser to great consciousness.”

though, there is a clear ethical implication to integral ecology. As Mary Jo Leddy puts it in her book, *Why Are We Here*, our future depends on a *profound* shift in our attitudes to this place on Earth we inhabit.⁴⁰ The word ‘profound’ is the critical word here. What we are facing with is not an ordinary change in our attitudes: we are asked to be ethical in a way that allows present (*hinc et nunc*) and future generations (our brothers and sisters, or to use another family-based image, to our sons and daughters of tomorrow) to flourish.⁴¹

1.6. Integral ecology: Dialogue, common good, solidarity and dignity of all

Haitians: David E. DeCosse has argued that one of the most innovative aspects of *Laudato Si’* with regard to the tradition is its development of the principle of the common good.⁴² Whereas Catholic Social Teaching has long held that this principle emanates from that of human dignity, Pope Francis amplifies that intuition by tying it to the intrinsic value of not only humans, but also non-human beings and ecosystems, and to his emphasis on the interconnectedness of all beings. This robust understanding of the common good allows for new possibilities for dialogue.

In Haiti, for example, social and political conflict is a major problem. Since most Haitians are people of faith, they have tried to find common ground through God-language. Yet because their religious identities are also diverse, religion also is a potential source of tension. Pope Francis offers a different entry point: consensus might be easier to find if we start by discussing “our common home.” Even though, as we have seen, there is no guarantee of

⁴⁰ Mary Jo Leddy, *Why Are We Here: A Meditation on Canada*. (Toronto: Novalis, 2019), 87: moving from being owner to becoming inhabitant. See also: Leddy Mary Jo. *The Other Face of God: When the Stranger Calls Us Home* (Maryknoll, N.Y: Orbis Books, 2011).

⁴¹ Thomas Berry. *The Great Work: Our Way into the Future* (Chapter 9: Ethics and Ecology).

⁴² David E. DeCosse and Brian Patrick Green, “Excerpts from *Laudato Si’* for Discussion in Class.” <https://www.scu.edu/media/ethics-center/environmental-ethics/encyclical-handout.pdf> (accessed August 13th, 2022).

objectivity in debates about climate change, its real effects are more immediate and less politicized for many in Haiti; people can more easily let their guard down and think in terms of solidarity when talking about the common good as “our common home,” making dialogue more fruitful. Further, as Pope Francis has shown us, talking about the environment will eventually lead us to engaging with *all* our concerns.

1.7. *The members of the human body in dialogue:* Relationship among people fits in the framework of the papal understanding of “integral ecology,” in the sense of “being in communication” or “being in communion,” given the idea that people are connected to each other. As Scripture puts it, “For as in one body we have many parts, and all the parts do not have the same function, so we, though many, are one body in Christ and individually parts of one another” (Romans 12: 4-5 NABRE). The more people are interconnected with each other, the more they are connected (or they are called to be connected) with the entirety of God’s Creation. Integral ecology has to do with a real and frank dialogue between two or more people because integral ecology is about the creation and cultivation of relationship. It also has a moral and spiritual dimension: “An integral ecology [the notion of dialogue] is inseparable from the notion of the common good, a central and unifying principle of social ethics. The common good is ‘the sum of those conditions of social life which allow social groups and their individual members relatively thorough and ready access to their own fulfillment.’”⁴³

One of the common obstacles to dialogue in the Haitian context is the inability to sit down *quietly* and listen *attentively* the others. It is also one of the dangers to the common good since many Haitians tend to put their personal interest over the interests of the community. Many

⁴³ LS 156.

Haitian compatriots lose the sense of what it means to be communal in the sense of “res-publica” (the communal thing, the common good). It is hard for many to differentiate what is communal from what is personal. And indeed, corruption (rampant in Haiti) often means (ab)using what is communal for personal gain.

1.8. Human solidarity leads to solidarity toward other-than-humans: The loving care that exists between people leads to solidarity. Solidarity between humans, in turn, will be beneficial for humans as well as for the natural world. In his novel, *The Masters of the Dew*, Jacques Roumain shows how, when the relationship that exists between people of the same living community is broken, the victims will include those members of the living community that are unseen or left behind because they are not human.⁴⁴ Like humanity (members of the Earth community), the remaining members of the same community could be counted among the “little ones” of the Bible within this community. In light of Pope Francis’s inclusion of non-human realities among the poor in *Laudato Si’*, Roumain’s famous novel can be read in a new light.

In Haiti, “[the] on-going clearing away of everything green is aggravated and encouraged by current unsustainable construction [known as *bidonvilles*] and mal-development trends.”⁴⁵ Deforestation is one among the common ‘evil’ activities Haitians continue to perform. The reason why these activities are so common might be surprising. Deforestation has become one of the main sources of income for families. The reason why the cutting down of the trees is evil is because it destroys the commons: it leads to erosion, which in turn causes dangerous mudslides, and contributes to climate change. The key here is finding alternative, sustainable sources of

⁴⁴ Roumain Jacques. *Gouverneurs de la Rosée*, dans : Jacques Roumain, Œuvres complètes, édition critique coordonnée par Léon-François Hoffmann. Nanterre, ALLCA/Paris Ediciones Unesco («Archivos» 58), 2003, 290-380.

⁴⁵ William Holden, Kathleen Nadeau and Emma Porio, *Ecological Liberation Theology: Faith-Based Approaches to Poverty and Climate Change in the Philippines* (Cham: Springer International Publishing: 2017), 7.

income for poor families – alternative sources that bring life and dignity to all the members of the Earth community.⁴⁶

1.9. Human dignity reciprocating into the “dignity”/worth of others: The person who testifies that he/she is a person with dignity knows how to teach values (as in Lonergan’s scale of values) and how to put values into reality. “We have only one heart, and the same wretchedness which leads us to mistreat an animal will not be long in showing itself in our relationships with other people. Every act of cruelty towards any creature – human and non-human entities – is ‘contrary to human dignity.’”⁴⁷ We cannot be a human person – that is, a person with dignity – and be merciless at the same time. We cannot reconcile the two things in a human – dignity and mercy – that are worthy of being called human. This applies, for example, to the issue of plastic waste: we are called to reuse things instead of immediately discarding them; this can be an act of love, which expresses our own dignity.⁴⁸

While Pope Francis has certainly made original contributions to the tradition, his ideas are rooted in the fundamental principles of Catholic Social Teaching, as expressed by his predecessors. Saint Pope John Paul II, who was prolific in this regard, is the only pope to have visited Haiti, which he did in 1983, during the Duvalier dictatorship. During that visit, he insisted that effective changes were needed in order for Haiti to move forward toward a true development that aims to be durable and sustainable. Four years later, his words again resonated strongly for Haiti, this time in an encyclical:

⁴⁶ Paul Farmer. *Haiti after the Earthquake*. Edited by Abbey Gardner and Cassia Van Der Hoof Holstein (New York: PublicAffairs, 2012), 35-36.

⁴⁷ LS 92.

⁴⁸ LS 211.

At the same time, in a world divided and beset by every type of conflict, the conviction is growing of a radical interdependence and consequently of the need for a solidarity which will take up interdependence and transfer it to the moral plane. Today perhaps more than in the past, people are realizing that they are linked together by a common destiny, which is to be constructed together, if catastrophe for all is to be avoided. From the depth of anguish, fear and escapist phenomena like drugs, typical of the contemporary world, the idea is slowly emerging that the good to which we are all called and the happiness to which we aspire cannot be obtained without an effort and commitment on the part of all, nobody excluded, and the consequent renouncing of personal selfishness.⁴⁹

What Saint Pope John Paul II is describing is what is known in Haitian culture as “tèt ansanm” (heads together) and “men nan men” (hand-in-hand). The two Haitian Creole expressions were tools of unity and solidarity between slaves of the colony of Saint-Domingue, whose metropolis was France. The efficacy and the efficiency of these tools – signs of their interconnectedness as people of one nation – have helped the Haitians to become the first black republic in the world, with the national motto, *l’union fait la force* (unity is strength).

It seems to me that what we need with regard to today’s challenges related to unity and solidarity is “mache ansanm” (walking/journeying together). We only face our problem and bear abundant fruits when we journey together. This essential part of synodality – working together since we are walking/journeying together – to which all (as citizens of world) are invited takes self-knowledge as well as knowledge and acknowledgement of the others (as different and not necessarily negative). It also requires the processes of individual and collective conversion (*metanoia*).

⁴⁹ Saint Pope John Paul II. Encyclical Letter *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis* (Vatican City: Vatican Press, 1987), 26.

CHAPTER TWO: (Integral) Ecology in Haiti and the Haitian Church

This chapter describes the social, political, and economic ecologies of Haiti – a developing country – focusing mainly on the environment and ecology in the aftermath of the devastating 2010 earthquake. Without pretending to analyze any of them exhaustively, each will be succinctly discussed, with one or two examples from the Haitian context for each sub-section, in order to illustrate the way all these ecologies are interwoven with each other.

2.1. General context of integral ecology in Haiti: When it comes to integral ecology, Haiti is not exempt from the challenges of complexity. If the environment in Haiti continues to worsen – mainly through deforestation, pollution of the air and water,⁵⁰ erosion of the fertile lands, and waste – this will negatively affect not only the ecosystem of the island but also that of the entire world’s ecosystems, given that the way ecosystems work is like a chain, in which every link affects the functioning of the overall/whole system.⁵¹ Daily efforts and commitments

⁵⁰ Pope Francis states: “Account must also be taken of the pollution produced by residue, including dangerous waste present in different areas. Each year hundreds of millions of tons of waste are generated, much of it non-biodegradable, highly toxic and radioactive, from homes and businesses, from construction and demolition sites, from clinical, electronic and industrial sources. The earth, our home, is beginning to look more and more like an immense pile of filth. In many parts of the planet, the elderly lament that once beautiful landscapes are now covered with rubbish. Industrial waste and chemical products utilized in cities and agricultural areas can lead to bioaccumulation in the organisms of the local population, even when levels of toxins in those places are low. Frequently no measures are taken until after people’s health has been irreversibly affected.” *LS*, 21. The Pope makes a clear statement about different types of pollution that come from different types of waste (material and immaterial ones). We are so used to hear terms such as “pollution of air” and “pollution of the water,” yet both are part of what has been called “material pollution,” which differs from “numeric pollution”.

⁵¹ Selon Jean Marie Jean Claude Germain, Ex-Ministre de l’Environnement, “l’utilisation du bois [et non du pétrole car Haïti est loin d’en être un pays producteur] à des fins énergétiques constitue l’une des principales raisons du déboisement en Haïti. D’après les estimations, près de 50 millions d’arbres et d’arbustes sont coupés chaque année pour des raisons énergétiques, alors que la capacité de régénération de ce qui existe [du forêt haïtien] ne dépasse pas 1,6 millions de mètre cube. Cette situation est à l’origine de la déforestation et de l’érosion des sols, et par conséquent de la diminution de la productivité agricole.” (“The use of wood [and not fossil fuel because Haiti is far from being an exporting country] for energy purposes is one of the main reasons for deforestation in Haiti. According to estimates, nearly 50 million trees and shrubs are cut down each year for energy reasons, while the regenerative capacity of what exists in the Haitian forest does not exceed 1.6 million cubic meters. This is the cause of deforestation and soil erosion, and consequently the decrease in agricultural productivity.”) Quote in Godefroy

in ecological matters have been made within and outside of Haiti, and they are beneficial for all members of the earth's biodiversity at large. In this chapter, I will consider some of the aspects of the integral ecology of my own country, Haiti. In doing so, both its environmental (non-human) dimension as well as its social (human) dimensions, and the connections between them, must be considered. With this in mind,

The two countries [of the island of Haiti: the Dominican Republic and the Republic of Haiti] have the same environment with the same biodiversity and practically the same problems even if some are more accentuated in one state [that is, in Haiti] than in the other. However, two political administrations, which have not yet learned to look together for common solutions to common challenges, make it a separate and isolated management, even if an evolution seems to be emerging today in favor of better cooperation in all the domains, the environment included.⁵²

One of the reasons the problem is accentuated more in the Republic of Haiti than in the Dominican Republic is the former's lack of technological advances. Haiti is poor scientifically speaking, and by extension, it is technologically poor as well. Technological innovation has to come to the entire island of Haiti – that is, to both countries, the Dominican Republic and Haiti – and it has to be used to indistinctively alleviate the human condition of all those who inhabit the island while serving the insular ecosystems of the island of Haiti and not the contrary.⁵³

Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise. Une lecture spirituelle ignacienne de la réalité actuelle (d'Haïti)* (Port-au-Prince: Centre de Recherche, de Réflexion, de Formation et d'Action Sociale-CERFAS, 2014), 62-63. Hereafter this book will be cited as : Godefroy Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise*.

⁵² Haiti is both the Indigenous name for the entire island and the name of one of the two nation-states that share the island today. Maismy-Mary Fleurant. *La gestion Durable des Cours d'Eau Transfrontaliers de la République Dominicaine et D'Haïti. Problématique, constats et perspectives* (Port-au-Prince: Centre de Recherche, de Réflexion, de Formation et d'Action Sociale-CERFAS, 2014), 29. « Les deux pays ont le même environnement avec la même biodiversité et pratiquement les mêmes problèmes même si certains sont plus accentués dans un Etat que dans l'autre. Cependant, deux administrations politiques, qui n'ont pas encore appris chercher ensemble des solutions communes aux défis communs, en font une gestion séparée et isolée, même si une évolution semble aujourd'hui se profiler en faveur d'une meilleure coopération dans tous les domaines, l'environnement inclus ».

⁵³ Maismy-Mary Fleurant. *La gestion Durable des Cours d'Eau Transfrontaliers*, 56-57 : « La République Dominicaine n'est, certes, pas responsable du retard technologique de son voisin, retard qui l'empêche de jouir pleinement de la ressource [en eau]. Cependant, il faut déjà poser des balises pour une gestion durable de l'eau. Car,

However, technological innovation is not necessarily a solution in and of itself. Like ecosystems, society is also interconnected from the local to the (inter)national and from below (i.e., the grassroots communities) to above (i.e., the elite). At the same time, we are living today in a divided world which is constantly evolving, and that ongoing division affects both the environmental and social dimensions of the crisis we are experiencing today. This is partly due to the technocratic paradigm, which would attempt to solve all problems exclusively through technological fixes, without realizing that the way technology is designed and used is not neutral, and that even if technology can make long-distance communication easier, it cannot heal our divisions and disconnections on its own.⁵⁴

This crisis puts at risk our [interior] peace in terms of living together with others in a harmonious manner. It is important to remember the following statement of Pope Francis as found in *Laudato Si'*: firstly, “an integral ecology calls for openness to categories which transcend the language of mathematics and biology [i.e. the mere language of science (whose main tool is technology) taken *alone* as the unique solution for all the problems of the world], and take us to the heart of what it is to be human.”⁵⁵ And secondly, an “integral ecology and the full development of humanity should now go together (that is, hand in hand) since a true development of women and men should necessarily bring them out of themselves and make them more open to God, to the other women and men, to nature and to themselves.”⁵⁶ The relationships of Haitian people to God, to people of the other parts of the planet, to nature, and to

le jour où Haïti aura les moyens techniques d'exploitation et réclamera un partage équitable [selon le principe d'utilisation équitable raisonnable de la ressource et celui de participation], cela pourra entraîner de nouvelles tensions dans les relations entre les deux États sans compter le risque d'une utilisation excessive. »

⁵⁴ LS 106-114. See also DeCosse and Green. “Excerpts from *Laudato Si* for Discussion in Class.”

⁵⁵ LS 11

⁵⁶ cf. LS 62

themselves *here* are extremely important. We must especially notice that, speaking in broad terms, the crisis of relationships (of any kind) will necessarily lead to an ecological crisis that will have to do with either the human/social or the natural/environmental or with both dimensions.⁵⁷

2.2. *The environmental/natural ecology of Haiti in the aftermath of the earthquake in 2010 and in 2021:* Kawas François, Renand Dorélien and Alexis Yves Blanchard observe that, “It was in a context of crisis in the urban development sector, of a policy of laxism (or *laissez-faire*) in terms of habitat and housing, of the abandonment to their fate of the most disadvantaged strata of the population that the 2010-earthquake occurred with its procession of death and destruction.”⁵⁸ Besides the years of recurrent crises of all types, this earthquake (known as the *Goudougoudou*, an onomatopoeic reference to the noise it made) has tremendously changed the face of Haiti and dramatically increased its environmental problems. Indeed, “integral ecology is about the [realization] that environmental issues cannot be dissociated from social, political, economic and cultural issues.”⁵⁹

⁵⁷ Capaldi Nicholas. “A Critique of Pope Francis’ ‘Laudato Si.’” *Seattle University law review* 40, no. 4 (2017): 1262: “Pope Francis characterizes the problem not simply as an environmental crisis but as an ecological crisis. It is ecological in the sense that he links the environment with poverty, specifically by claiming that there is an intimate relationship between the poor and the fragility of the planet.”

⁵⁸ Kawas François, Renand Dorélien et Alexis Yves Blanchard. *Relogement des Personnes Déplacées par suite du Tremblement de Terre du 12 Janvier 2010* (Port-au-Prince : Centre de Recherche, de Réflexion, de Formation et d’Action Sociale-CERFAS, 2014), 25 : « C’est dans un contexte de crise du secteur de développement urbain, d’une politique de laisser-faire en matière d’habitat et de logement, d’abandon à leur sort des couches les plus défavorisées de la population, que survint le tremblement de terre du 12 Janvier 2010, avec son cortège de morts et de destruction. ».

⁵⁹ Dermot Lane et al., *Theology and Ecology in Dialogue*, 25.

Both the natural⁶⁰ ecology of Haiti and the country's infrastructure has been critically damaged and in many instances destroyed due to two major earthquakes that hit the country in 2010 and 2021, respectively. How to rebuild Haitian society and its living environment? According to Pope Francis, we have the human/social category on the one hand, and the environmental category on the other, since both are the two wings of the same bird (metaphorically speaking) that is called ecology.⁶¹ To speak of the environmental/natural ecology of Haiti is to some extent to speak of all “non-human” realities, such as biodiversity, that contribute to make Haitian life livable. We are called to live and make a living in the midst of this diversity, in spite of some imminent life events/contingencies (natural disasters or hazards and social difficulties) that constantly affect us, specifically as Caribbean peoples and ethnic groups.

The devastating *Goudougoudou* adversely affected the Haitian people in their very being.⁶² The reconstruction of Haitian society on so many different levels – particularly on the human level – will take ongoing investment of both time and energy (or resources). This will be made possible when we really come to “recognize the importance of moral and spiritual education for sustainable living.”⁶³

⁶⁰ The qualifier “environmental” is often used interchangeably with the term “natural.” The word “natural” with respect to (integral) ecology encompasses human and non-human entities while the word “environmental” does not because it is more restrictive: it denotes everything that surrounds humanity, without including humanity which is the referent point. However, both words can be considered to be synonymous to some extent.

⁶¹ *LS 49*: “Today, however, we have to realize that a true ecological approach *always* becomes a social approach; it must integrate questions of justice in debates on the environment, so as to hear both the cry of the earth and the cry of the poor.” I borrow this metaphor while referring here to Pope John Paul II’s analogy of the human spirit with his/her two wings: faith and reason that make him/her an integral being. See also: Boff Leonardo. *Cry of the Earth, Cry of the Poor* (Maryknoll, New York: Orbis Books, 1997).

⁶² See: Kawas François et al. *Relogement des Personnes Déplacées*, 20.

⁶³ Earth Charter International. 14 d, <https://earthcharter.org/library/the-earth-charter-booklet/> (accessed July 25th 2022).

We cannot speak of respect for the dignity of the human person, and of the Haitian person in particular, without taking into account his/her most fundamental human rights, i.e., rights recognized by the Universal Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen of the United Nations, such as education, health and housing.⁶⁴ These three interconnected rights have always been problematic in the Haitian historical context. However, due to the 2010 earthquake, the latter has become increasingly precarious. Despite the precarious situation in Haiti, the foreign aid necessary to rebuild the country is difficult, if not impossible, to raise. Kawas François, a Haitian Jesuit sociologist, sums up the situation as follows,

The humanitarian phase having come to an end, it was necessary, according to the schedule established with external cooperation, to move on to the reconstruction phase. But the declarations of intent of donors at the May 2010 meeting in New York for the financing of reconstruction projects did not materialize as planned in terms of actual disbursements and the major reconstruction projects never saw the light of day.⁶⁵

After a catastrophe like the 2010 earthquake in Haiti, short-term humanitarian aid is certainly needed to save people from the immediate aftermath and the disruption in food and other necessities. However, long-term aid for rebuilding is probably even more necessary and from a global perspective more integral to the common good. As François notes, though, international donors tend to ignore needs that require long term aid.⁶⁶

⁶⁴ See, Déclaration Universelle des Droits de l'Homme et du Citoyen. Nous ne pouvons pas parler du respect de la dignité de la personne humaine et de l'homme haïtien en particulier sans tenir compte de ses droits plus fondamentaux reconnus par la Déclaration Universelle des Droits de l'Homme et du Citoyen des Nations Unies: éducation, santé et logement pour ne citer que ces trois-là dans le cadre de ce projet..

⁶⁵ Kawas François et al., *Relogement des Personnes Déplacées*, 21 : « Le tremblement de terre de 12 janvier 2010 aura porté la question du logement au rang d'urgence nationale, particulièrement dans l'aire métropolitaine de Port-au-Prince et dans les villes les plus touchées. Les interventions observées dans ce secteur ne semblent répondre à aucun plan cohérent dûment acceptée par les instances concernées. La question qui se pose est de savoir dans quelle mesure les logements construits pour accueillir les familles déplacées par suite de la catastrophe sont conformes aux normes nationales et internationales en la matière et aux attentes des populations. »

⁶⁶ Kawas François et al., *Relogement des Personnes Déplacées*, 25-26.

2.3. Protecting biodiversity of the fauna and the flora: We are located in our own specific ecosystem, with its particular biodiversity which is embedded in a larger common home with even greater biodiversity.⁶⁷ This shared home is in danger.

Although we are often not aware of it, we depend on these larger systems for both our own life/existence and our survival. We need only recall how ecosystems interact in dispersing carbon dioxide, purifying water, controlling illnesses and epidemics [pandemics such as covid-19], forming soil, breaking down waste, and in many other ways which we overlook or simply ignore. Once they become conscious of this, many people realize that we live and act on the basis of a reality which has previously been given to us, which precedes our existence and our abilities.⁶⁸

Both the animals and plants that make up our local and regional ecosystems undergo some levels of abuse and mistreatment, which has gradually led many species and families of living beings to extinction. It becomes more obvious to Pope Francis that, “Each year sees the disappearance of thousands of plant and animal species which we will never know, which our children will never see, because they have been lost forever. *The great majority become extinct for reasons related to human activity.* Because of us, thousands of species will no longer give glory to God by their very existence, nor convey their message to us. We have no such right.”⁶⁹ Haiti is a vivid example since many species of both fauna and flora (species of birds, trees and plants of any kind) have become extinct.

⁶⁷ Ecofeminist theologian Heather Eaton states: “It is crucial to understand that “the earth understood as planetary is our common home. This image can be powerful *if and only if* situated within a larger framework (or biodiversity) which also includes the community of beings who also emerged from and belong to these immense, ingenious, and subtle planetary processes. There is no room for static realities within this common and shared home.” See, Heather Eaton, “An Earth-Centric Theological Framing for Planetary Solidarity” in Grace Ji-Sun Kim & Hilda P. Koster (eds.), *Planetary Solidarity: Global Women's Voices on Christian Doctrine and Climate Justice* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), 26.

⁶⁸ LS 140.

⁶⁹ LS 33, Italics are mine. Pope Francis makes use of the terms “human activity” while Thomas Berry and his companion Brian Swimme make use of the expression “human intrusion” to mean the same. However, human should not be an intrusion at all. See: Thomas Berry. *The Great Work*, 32: “The [truly] human is neither an addendum nor an intrusion into the universe. We are quintessentially integral with the universe.” See also: Brian Swimme and Thomas Berry. *The Universe Story. From The Primordial Flaring Forth to The Ecozoic Era* (New York: HarperSanFrancisco, 1992).

2.4. Protecting biodiversity while avoiding deforestation: In Haiti, deforestation is among the leading causes of biodiversity loss. It is also among the leading causes of extinction. For Pope Francis, it is a “determining factor has been an increase in changed uses of the soil.”⁷⁰ Indeed, this phenomenon affects the biodiversity of the land, the sea, and the air, since all of them are interconnected through the forest landscape.⁷¹ Birds find a habitat, or in some cases, migratory rest stops, in tree branches. The roots of trees prevent soil erosion, which would otherwise flow into the sea, cutting off light and oxygen from coral reefs. However, in Haiti as “in many [other] parts of the planet, the elderly [as well as some people of the new generation] lament that once beautiful landscapes are now covered with rubbish.”⁷²

Changing this reality depends on political will, but also ultimately on social awareness. In the Constitution of Haiti, the conditions of protection [or the preservation] of the fauna and flora are determined through legal decision-making from the Senate.⁷³ As Mgr. Pierre d'Ornell states :

⁷⁰ LS 23.

⁷¹ Like the land and the sea, the air is an important resource to be preserved. In some places, clean, breathable air (in the same way as the drinking and clean water) becomes more and more rare. Mgr. Pierre d'Ornellas states that “Il ne suffit pas d’identifier et de valoriser les ressources naturelles pour rendre notre économie plus humaine. Il s’agit de les préserver, sans oublier la première d’entre elles, qui est en voie de raréfaction un peu partout sur la planète : l’air respirable” [“[I]t is not enough to identify and value natural resources to make our economy more human. It is a question of preserving them, without forgetting the first of them, which is becoming rare all over the planet is breathable air” (The intended translation is mine)], Mgr. Pierre d'Ornellas *Pour une économie humaine*, (Paris: Salvator, 2017), 162.

⁷² LS 21.

⁷³ “La loi [mère] détermine les conditions de protection de la faune et de la flore. Elle sanctionne les contravenants .” (The english translation is mine). See: Article 258 of the Constitution de la République d’Haiti (1987) Available onlie at <https://www.haiti-reference.com/pages/plan/histoire-et-societe/documents-historiques/constitutions/1987-texte/>, (accessed May 31st, 2021). Like many laws, regulations, and other constitutions, The Haitian Constitution (the mother of all laws) makes statements related to the environment without having any executing power. Aware of the fact and with respect to what laws do (in general), Pope Francis, in his Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si’*, says what follows, “A number of countries have a relatively low level of institutional effectiveness, which results in greater problems for their people while benefiting those who profit from this situation. Whether in the administration of the state, the various levels of civil society, or relationships between individuals themselves, lack of respect for the law is becoming more common. Laws may be well framed yet remain a dead letter. Can we hope, then, that in such cases, legislation and regulations dealing with the environment will really prove effective? We know, for example, that countries which have clear legislation about the protection of

“The preservation of natural resources will only be possible if the public authorities ensure that populations are regularly made aware of ecological issues with elected driving forces who do not simply intervene in the world of reaction, following an ecological disaster, but out of conviction, on the long run.”⁷⁴

One challenge to environmental protection in Haiti is the need for economic growth. Finding a balance between economic growth or development and the proper use of the natural resources is quite a big challenge today for many countries, yet it is especially challenging for so called developing nations like Haiti. In order to achieve sustainable economic growth that does not further ravage Haiti’s natural environment, Haiti will need to dialogue with its neighbors, especially the Dominican Republic, with which it shares an island with interrelated ecosystems and transnational rivers and lakes.

Agriculture is a particularly sensitive economic activity, both in terms of its impact on people and on biodiversity. Here, too, the international policy context is key. However, developing sustainable policies in a way that is just to poor countries remains a challenge. As the Haitian legal scholar, Maismy-Mary Fleurant, has noted in his article “Agriculture in the Juridical International Regime of Climate”,

forests continue to keep silent as they watch laws repeatedly being broken. Moreover, what takes place in any one area can have a direct or indirect influence on other areas. Thus, for example, drug use in affluent societies creates a continual and growing demand for products imported from poorer regions, where behaviour is corrupted, lives are destroyed, and the environment continues to deteriorate.” (LS 142) See also: Mary Evelyn Tucker et al., *Thomas Berry: An Autobiography*, 149-150: “As Thomas saw it, even the United States Constitution is fundamentally flawed because it reserves all rights for humans and recognizes none for nature. For Thomas, the deficiency cries out for a fundamental transformation of our modern ideas of law. At the heart of this transformation, he noted, is the shift from a human-centered to an Earth-centered understanding of our relationship with the larger community of life. A profound change in perspective, he felt, would enable humans to recognize and protect the rights of the natural world”.

⁷⁴ Mgr. Pierre d'Ornellas. *Pour une économie humaine*, 164: “La préservation des ressources naturelles ne sera possible que si les pouvoirs publics veillent à sensibiliser régulièrement les populations sur les questions écologiques avec des élus moteurs qui n'interviennent pas simplement sur le monde de la réaction, suite à une catastrophe écologique, mais par conviction, sur le long court.”

Agriculture is undoubtedly one of the sectors most affected by climate change. While the sector is a major source of greenhouse gas emissions, adapting it remains a major challenge, especially for countries in the southern hemisphere, where agriculture is economically vital and represents a source of jobs and guaranteed food security. However, the international legal regime has not paid enough attention to the climate issue. This can be observed not only in conventional treaties, but also in the Decisions of the Conference of the Parties and even in the funding of financial mechanism projects and programs. Following the progress made at COP17, the Koronivia Joint Work is the most significant agricultural initiative in the climate regime. It will be necessary to continue its implementation with a view to achieving the establishment of a real plan of action for this sector.⁷⁵

Because Haiti is a tropical country, among the specific challenges the agricultural sector is facing are first and foremost the disastrous consequences of hurricanes and tropical cyclones. As an example, in 2016 during the passage of the hurricane named Matthew, a major part of the great South – particularly the greenest regions of the southwestern Grand’Anse department – lost all the vegetation that usually serves to feed the country’s capital (i.e., Port-au-Prince) and other urban centers. Additionally, the environmental degradation has worsened the risks of natural disasters and/or hazards while making the country even more vulnerable to flooding and to drought. Both *too much water* and *too little water* are life-threatening for the agricultural sector in Haiti because of the imbalance that has been created. The negative impacts of climate change and extreme weather events are compounded by equally serious social disasters and hazards, such as “the punishingly unfair political economy.”⁷⁶ Technological support for

⁷⁵ Maismy-Mary Fleurant, "L'Agriculture dans le Regime Juridique International du Climat," *Cahiers de Droit* 62, no. 3 (September 2021), 935-936.

⁷⁶ Paul Farmer. *Haiti after the Earthquake*. Edited by Abbey Gardner and Cassia Van Der Hoof Holstein (New York: PublicAffairs, 2012), 35. In addition to the agricultural challenges caused by natural disasters, Farmer sees the fact that few young Haitians wanted to work in a sector that offered diminishing returns as hindering the country’s progress.

agriculture could positively impact the environment in Haiti and guarantee sustainable development for Haitian peasants.⁷⁷

2.5. Protecting biodiversity while tackling clean water and (plastic) waste issues:

The sixth among the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) is Clean Water and Sanitation. The goal states that, “Clean, accessible water for all is an essential part of the world we want to live in.”⁷⁸ Access to clean water and waste management are big issues in Haiti. The former in many countries of the world is a right and not a privilege. Access to clean water should be so as well in the Haitian context as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights recognizes this as a right for all people without distinction. Nevertheless, in many overcrowded areas in Haiti, such as Village de Dieu in Martissant (Martyr-Sang), Site Solèy, Fil Ayopò, Canaan, Croix-des-Bouquets, etc. as well as in many developing countries of the world, people lack clean and fresh drinking water.

How to ensure universal access to drinking water, as Pope Francis asks us to do?⁷⁹ Although it appears to be a challenge, we can be more sensitive at least to those in need of water in order to survive. Being sensitive and aware of what is happening in our common and shared home can be our way of contributing to the cause.

⁷⁷ See: Mats Lundahl. *Peasants and Poverty: A Study of Haiti* (New York: Routledge Revivals: 2015), 616: “Haitian peasants agriculture has been technologically stagnant for more than a century. Early efforts by Henry Christophe to introduce the modern methods of the day failed, and instead the agricultural sector underwent a process of technological retrogression during early nineteenth century.” See also: Taylor Sarah McFarland. *Green Sisters: A Spiritual Ecology* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2009): 184: Green sisters stress the importance of working nature and [never] against it [while making use of technology], studying the earth’s ways of growing living things and ways of self-nourishing, and making human approaches to agriculture mimic this ‘earth wisdom’ as much as possible.”

⁷⁸ United Nations Report on Sustainable Development, Goal 6th on clean water and sanitation, <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/> (accessed May 12th, 2022).

⁷⁹ LS 164

Additionally, the managing of waste is and remains a real problem in Haiti since remote times. Every large city in Haiti has a waste management problem, in spite of the efforts of local governments to regularly clean the streets. We also know that clean roads do not only depend on the competence of the cleaning service crews but also on that of the people who make daily use of the road. Therefore, without an informed eco-education, we will not have the expected results. Ecological education or Eco-education – as the Pope suggests it for the entire world⁸⁰ – should become a must to encourage behaviors that are conducive to changes at both the social and the environmental of context of Haiti.

Plastic pollution constitutes for us our actual cancer.⁸¹ Although we do not produce plastic in Haiti, we are victims of the mercantile ideology (consumerism) of the market that is behind the importation of excessive amounts of plastic products. Once all the plastics have been sold and distributed, they will soon end up in the landfill as waste. Perhaps we should interpret Article 258 of the Haitian Constitution to apply to this case, where it states the following, “Nobody is permitted to introduce to the country any waste or residues, of whatever nature, from abroad.”⁸²

⁸⁰ *LS 211.*

⁸¹ Here is a papal reminder on the education we (as Haitians) have to long for. The challenges linked to this type of educations are enormous. See: *LS 211*: “Education in environmental responsibility can encourage ways of acting which directly and significantly affect the world around us, such as avoiding the use of plastic and paper, reducing water consumption, separating refuse, cooking only what can reasonably be consumed, showing care for other living beings, using public transport or car-pooling, planting trees, turning off unnecessary lights, or any number of other practices. All of these reflect a generous and worthy creativity which brings out the best in human beings. Reusing something instead of immediately discarding it, when done for the right reasons, can be an act of love which expresses our own dignity.”

⁸² Article 258 of the Constitution of Haiti (1987): “Nul ne peut introduire dans le Pays des déchets ou résidus de provenances étrangères de quelque nature que ce soit.”

Among the plastic debris, Styrofoam is a product that kills Haiti and her daughters and sons. However, Styrofoam, which is a renowned pollutant and poison,⁸³ has circulated throughout Haiti for decades, mainly in the food industry. Even though Haiti does not produce the Styrofoam, it remains a faithful client of plastic products of all types. The main sources of the importation of the many Styrofoam products found in Haiti are unclear. These products, however, seem to arrive mainly from the Dominican Republic, which is one of the transit routes for the product to get access to the country.

Some scientists have suggested that Styrofoam could be an opportunity, since we might transform the plastic waste into fuel that can be used for the entire population through a Circular Economy process.⁸⁴ Like many other plastic waste products, Styrofoam can be used to extract petroleum by the method of pyrolysis. This method has been used in many countries. It is not clear however whether the pyrolysis or decomposition process is a risk-free chemical process. This is a dilemma for Haiti, especially since technology is not the country's greatest strength. Using the precautionary principle, we should not proceed when the side effects of decomposing plastic are not fully known. The implications and involvements in the damages on future generations should be studied and taken into account.⁸⁵

⁸³ Jang Mi, Won Joon Shim, Gi Myung Han, Manviri Rani, Young Kyoung Song, and Sang Hee Hong. "Styrofoam Debris as a Source of Hazardous Additives for Marine Organisms." *Environmental science & technology* 50, no. 10 (2016): 4951–4960.

⁸⁴ For more elaboration on the circular economy as a solution to address the ecological crisis, see Miguel Brandão, David, Lazarevic, and Göran, Finnveden (eds). *Handbook of the Circular Economy* (Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020). For something even more concise see Walter R. Stahel "The circular economy." *Nature* 531, 435–438 (2016) and Vanessa Prieto-Sandoval, Carmen Jaca, and Marta Ormazabal. "Towards a Consensus on the Circular Economy." *Journal of cleaner production* 179 (2018): 605–615.

⁸⁵ See Roise Cooney and Barney Dickson. *Biodiversity and the Precautionary Principle: Risk and Uncertainty in Conservation and Sustainable Use* (London: Earthscan, 2005).

2.6. Social ecology: cumulative crisis of values: Pope Francis says, “When the foundations of social life are corroded, what ensues are battles over conflicting interests, new forms of violence and brutality, and obstacles to the growth of a genuine culture of care for the environment.”⁸⁶ Most of the people of the Haitian society – whether they are inside or outside of the country – often ignore the question of *what makes us very truly humans?* Slowly but surely, many tend to lose the deeper meaning of life. Being human – or pertaining to this category we call humanity – is all about being social (that is, not being an isolated being but being in relationship with others: both with other humans like us and with non-human beings) in a specific moment while occupying a particular place. “There can be no renewal of our relationship with nature without a renewal of humanity itself. There can be no ecology [a sense of relationship of members of a same community] without an adequate anthropology [a sense of self].”⁸⁷ Being in relationships *here and now* with others means caring for all of them while loving them and serving them. The reason why we care for all of them is because we are not only *with* them, in the sense of being together with the other members of the community, but also *for* them, in the sense of being responsible, committed to each and every other member of this community. We are called to be men and women *with* and *for* others (for the Haitians as well as for the non-Haitians). What would happen if we do not respond adequately to this challenging call?

One should keep in mind that responding to the invitation and/or call to love and serve is not an easy thing to do. The call is given to each of us as an opportunity to act. If we do not

⁸⁶ LS 229. Social life can negatively affect the environmental milieu in the same way that social ecology can have positive impact on the environmental ecology through a growing awareness and desire to improve our relationship as human beings.

⁸⁷ LS 118.

respond properly to this call to love and serve, we will see ourselves falling into a cumulative (and unwanted) crisis of values.⁸⁸ Neither the human nor the non-human entities will be taken into consideration for their value (or virtue) as they are all subjects, channels for God's presence and action.⁸⁹ The human being – *Imago Dei* where dignity and respect flow – is becoming valued less in this perspective, since we fall into key social issues that we already know and to which we are accustomed. Simultaneously, if we do not take our responsibility for the non-human realities – in which God is also present and active – they lose value for us since we fall into the main environmental problems such as pollution, management of waste, erosion, deforestation or cutting down of trees, etc.

We are constantly navigating between these two different big issues or crises (social and environmental), as some would put it. However, having a more integral vision, Pope Francis in *Laudato Si'* goes further when he says that they are not two different, separated issues or crises but a single that is complex,⁹⁰ a crisis with two wings: the social (human affairs) and the environmental (non-human affairs). This way of looking at the issue or crisis is deeply informed by the Pope's theology of creation, which is crucial for this thesis project also.

⁸⁸ Fritjof Capra. "Deep Ecology. A New Paradigm", George Sessions (ed.). *Deep Ecology for the 21st Century* (Boston: Random House, 1994), 24: "The shift to a new worldview and a new mode of thinking goes hand in hand with a profound change in values [together with new attitudes and lifestyles]. What is so fascinating about these changes, to me, is a striking connection between the change of thinking [or perhaps de principles] and the change of value. Both can be seen as a shift from self-assertion to integration. As far as thinking is concerned, we can observe a shift from the rational to the intuitive, from analysis to synthesis, from reductionism to holism, from linear to non-linear thinking."

⁸⁹ Heather Eaton, "An Earth-Centric Theological Framing for Planetary Solidarity", 31: "Hildegard von Bingen and Thomas Aquinas studied cosmological and Earth sciences and built a theological edifice on the precept that creation is wholesome and permeated with divine presence. Life and existence are worthy, and God is present [and even active/dynamic]. The natural world is a place of divine revelation, as primary, secondary, or parallel to the customary Christian notions of revelation". This point made by Eaton regarding the two great figures Hildegard von Bingen and Aquinas is so relevant. See also: Leonardo Boff. *Toward an Eco-Spirituality*. Translated by Robert H. Hopke (New York State: Crossroad Publishing Company, 2015), 43: "If we cannot rescue the sacred, it will be difficult to respect the Earth and the intrinsic value of other human [and non-human, I would say] beings."

⁹⁰ LS 139.

In this light, two among many civic duties of the Haitian citizen as stated in the Haitian Constitution stand out. The first duty is to “respect and protect the environment” while the second one is to “work in order to maintain peace.”⁹¹ This idea of caring for ecology in order to be in peace shows how being interconnected through love is so important.⁹² Pope Francis shows how, through a logic of subsidiarity and given the planetary interconnectedness of integral ecology, this civic duty is part of global citizenship:

Because all creatures are connected, each must be cherished with love and respect, for all of us as living creatures are dependent on one another. Each area is responsible for the care of this family. This will require undertaking a careful inventory of the species which it hosts, with a view to developing programmes and strategies of protection with particular care for safeguarding species heading towards extinction.⁹³

However, the history of Hispaniola – which includes Haiti and the Dominican Republic – demonstrates how this ideal is not always actualized. The plundering of natural resources within a habitat can devolve into a tool of genocide. The entire autochthonous nation known as Arawaks (or Tainos) was exterminated during the Spanish colonial period starting in the late 15th century. That was genocide. From the social and cultural genocide of the native population of Arawaks, we have moved on to the linked concept of ecocide, i.e., the killing of their natural environment, following the same logic of murderous domination due to the excesses of the anthropocentric mindset. The way of the plundering natural resources, causing the disappearance of the habitat among other things, is in fact a tool of genocide. The natural environment has been seen as a

⁹¹ Article 52.1 of the Constitution de la République d’Haiti (1987). Available online at <https://www.haiti-reference.com/pages/plan/histoire-et-societe/documents-historiques/constitutions/1987-texte/> (accessed May 31st, 2021).

⁹² I want to refer here to Lonergan’s notion of the religious value in which *being in love with God* which is highest rank in the scale of values leads to the love of others (including that of the other members of nature or creation as a whole). See: Bernard J. F. Lonergan. *Philosophical and Theological Papers, 1965-1980*. Edited by Robert C. Croken and Robert M. Doran (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2004), 38: “Being in love with God, as experienced, is being in love in an unrestricted fashion. All love is self-surrender but being in love with God is being in love without limits or qualifications or conditions or reservations.”

⁹³ LS 42.

resource or “mere thing” for us to do with as we please instead of a gift to be protected and appreciated.

The idea of integral ecology does not permit the objectification of the nature. Because it comprises both the environmental and the social dimension of ecology, the ecological cannot be isolated from the human realm. The ecological crisis and dysfunctional social ecology of Haiti, which is mainly characterized by a cumulative crisis of values, is intensified by a dysfunctional political ecology and economic ecology, both of which are within the same social realm.

2.7. Political ecology with the mentality of « *Jusqu’au boutisme* » [until putting an end to] and economic ecology: The current economic crisis is in some ways an apolitical one. The concept of “apolitical” refers to a failed regime, where politics is totally discredited due to the corruption of political actors, the generalization of public deficits and the non-respect of state budgets. The attitudes and behaviors of political leaders are similar to what we (following Saint Augustine) can call laziness, that is to say, the absence of courage, creativity, planning and foresight. Routine carelessness prevails.⁹⁴ We observe a questioning of the rights and values of private property, the multiplication and strengthening of networks engaged in corruption, drugs and human trafficking. The state is increasingly losing control of armed groups and of ever larger portions of the national territory. We live under the constant threat of a return to dictatorship with an Executive that governs by decree and often in defiance of the Constitution. Notorious bandits and criminals – some of whom are supposedly wanted by the police – openly intervene in the political arena and in the media. This deleterious political climate unfolds against a backdrop of deep social problems: generalized and worrying degradation of living conditions, which leads

⁹⁴ Saint Augustine. *City of God*, XII, 17. Abridged and translated by JWC Wand (London: Oxford University Press), 1963.

to the flight of human and financial capital (about 84% of those who have passed the bac II [grade school] in recent years leave the country), which in turn leads to the glaring absence of human resources in all social sectors and the increasingly notable phenomenon of social and economic exiles.

The part affects the whole. The more humanity loses a sense of personal virtue, the more a sense of a more communal virtue is lost as well. Both the personal and the social affect the political, which can be understood as the common ground of life for all the inhabitants of the *polis* (or the city or the community).

Political ecology is defined as the intersection between politics and ecology that pays particular attention to addressing the ecological crisis through good policy. Political ecology deals with the question of how ecology could first and foremost be inspired by the constitution and the decent laws voted by the citizenry for their present good and that of the future generations.⁹⁵ Because of the corruption and disregard for the common good, Haiti needs a national political agenda that places integral ecology at the center of all human activities. In other words, an established national policy plan whose aim is to take “the other” (i.e., anything different than the self) into account is all what we need and deserve. However, part of the lack of the recognition of the other has to do with the mentality of “*Jusqu’au boutisme*”⁹⁶ or “*rache manyòk*” [uprooting the manioc] that is almost always present in our way of doing politics, whose full meaning is inscribed in this slogan “*vle pa vle, fò l ale*” (whether you – as Haitian

⁹⁵ We have to notice the evolution of the definitions of the concepts of “political ecology” (opposed to the always existing “apolitical ecology”) with all the layers and nuances. See: Robbins Paul. *Political Ecology: An Introduction*. Third Edition. (New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons Ltd, 2020), 10-11.

⁹⁶ Although the term is of frequent use, explicit mention of it was made to refer to citizens of the Arab context with extremist political ideologies. See: Ahmed Ajil. *Politico-ideological Mobilisation and Violence in the Arab World: All In* (New York: Taylor & Francis, 2023), 194.

president or elected representative – want it or not, you should leave power; this slogan is often applied not long after formal investiture).

Nourished by the same slogan, *rache mayòk bay tè a blanch* is a way of doing politics that uses the metaphor of uprooting the manioc (an edible root and staple food), in reference to clearing the ground of the political system. In this view, the political machinery that is currently in operation should be “cleared” entirely. Starting with the uprising that removed the dictatorship of the Duvalier family, the rhetoric of *rache manyòk* constitutes a clear message, directed even today to any established government, to get out of the way (i.e., out of the political scene) without conditions. Although the Constitution stipulates a five-year term for presidents, Haiti often witnesses a political crisis with calls for regime change after only two or three years.

As in the famous Jacques Roumain novel, *Gouverneurs de la Rosée* (*Masters of the Dew*), ecology in Haiti is inseparable from history, society, culture, religion, politics and economics.⁹⁷ Politics and economics in Haiti are two interconnected realms. The Pope observes that, “Many of those who possess more resources and economic or political power seem mostly to be concerned with masking the problems or concealing their symptoms, simply making efforts to reduce some of the negative impacts of climate change. However, many of these symptoms indicate that such effects will continue to worsen if we continue with current models of production and consumption.”⁹⁸ In Haiti, we no longer produce an abundance of sugar,

⁹⁷ Jacques Roumain. *Gouverneurs de la Rosée*, dans : Jacques Roumain, *Œuvres complètes*, édition critique coordonnée par Léon-François Hoffmann. Nanterre, ALLCA/Paris Ediciones Unesco («Archivos» 58), 2003, pp. 290-.380. *C'est pas Dieu qui abandonne le nègre, c'est le nègre qui abandonne la terre et il reçoit sa punition : la sécheresse, la misère et la désolation* et c'est à partir de là que nous faisons face à toutes sortes de problème écologique (social et environnemental). It is not God who abandons the negre, it is the negre who abandons the Earth and receives his punishment: drought, misery and desolation). Hereafter this novel is cited as Jacques Roumain. *Gouverneurs de la Rosée*.

⁹⁸ LS 26.

coffee, and tobacco for export as we did in the past when the country's economy was flourishing. Instead of an exporting country, Haiti's economy has grown dependent on imports and has a trade deficit. This is among the reasons why the economic situation in Haiti is precarious and is becoming even more precarious with the passing of time. In the next point, we talk about the transition from being in a precarious situation to being even more precarious. Today, Haiti is the poorest and most impoverished country in the Western Hemisphere and is on its way to become the poorest and the most impoverished country in the entire world.⁹⁹

From both the perspectives of its ecology and economy, Haiti thus moves from being poor to becoming poorer. Two years ago, the Superior of the Haitian Jesuit Territory explained in his own words the economic dimension of the crisis we are living in Haiti. What he said continues to be of actuality since the crisis has been worsened,

The global crisis of our society has an eminently economic dimension. The latter has as indicators: the decline in production in all sectors of the national economy, the fall in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The latter amounted to 9.6 billion US dollars for the year 2019, or \$854 per capita. It remains insignificant, compared to that of the Dominican Republic which amounted to 75 billion US dollars during the same period. More than 60% of the country's population lives below the absolute poverty line. The vast majority of Haitians are unable to access basic social services including education. The rural exodus is in full swing; the peasants emigrate every day in great numbers towards the city in search of a job which unfortunately does not exist. We are witnessing an accumulation of trade and budget deficits in recent years, the embezzlement of public funds and the institutionalization of corruption, etc. The country currently imports almost everything: technologies, food products (meat, fish, milk), cars, medicines, fabrics, etc. This is daily accelerating the imbalance in the balance of payments with its many negative consequences both at the micro and macro level.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁹ There is a big difference between “being poor” and “being impoverished” (or “made poor”). In the case of Haiti, the country is both poor (for internal reasons) and impoverished (for external reasons). See: Alexis Yves Blanchard, Kawas François and Joseph Chéry (ed.). *Désastres Naturels, Violence Sociale et Déplacements Forcés de Population en Haïti*. Port-au-Prince : Centre de Recherche, de Réflexion, de Formation et d'Action Sociale-CERFAS, 2011), 33. Hereafter, this book will be cited as: Alexis Yves Blanchard et al. (ed.). *Désastres Naturels, Violence Sociale*.

¹⁰⁰ Jean-Denis Saint-Félix, SJ. « Haiti, ten years after the earthquake: An interview », IN: <https://jesuits.ca/press-release/haiti-ten-years-after-the-earthquake-an-interview-with-jean-denis-saint-felix-sj/> accessed July 25, 2022. Hereafter, this article will be cited as: Jean-Denis Saint-Félix, SJ. « Haiti, ten years after the earthquake ».

Economic ecology refers to the relationship that exists between economy and ecology. Most experts agree that our ecology is in crisis, and many see the cause of this as related to economic systems. According to Charles Russ Beaton and Chris Maser in their book, *Economics and Ecology: United for a Sustainable World*, there are two sides to this crisis – our global economy which is most often motivated by human greed or avarice, and its effect on the ecology and ecosystems of our home planet Earth. Despite our conventional ways of thinking that monetary and fiscal manipulations will put us back on the path of economic growth, the reality is not that simple.¹⁰¹ Economic growth is more than the mere use and exchange of money. Meanwhile, “the natural environment is sending unmistakable warnings. Glaciers are melting in the North; oceans are becoming dangerously acidic in the South; species and their ecological services are becoming extinct in both parts; and weather patterns are becoming increasingly severe and unpredictable each year all over the planet. The stress on resource systems of all kinds threatens to shrink the carrying capacity of the planet, even as we call upon it for increased contributions to support a burgeoning human population.”¹⁰²

In Haiti, our agriculture-based economy is quite weak and due to lack of technological capabilities, fails to enhance ecosystems, let alone protect them from greater risk. Haiti’s natural beauty has degraded tremendously due a panoply of reasons: the selling of our mountains for building purposes (which leads to frequent floods and landslides), deforestation, mining activities (which lead to damage and even disappearance of living communities and habitats). Unfortunately, Haiti does not have strong environmental regulations that guarantee the right of

¹⁰¹ See Charles Russ Beaton and Chris Maser. *Economics and Ecology: United for a Sustainable World* (Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press-Taylor & Francis Group, 2012), xiii.

¹⁰² Beaton and Maser. *Economics and Ecology*, 193.

both the society and the environment. Because of its deep impoverishment, the focus is on the social-economic realm. Yet, the two are interrelated: “To instill some vital energy to an anemic economy, the forest is excessively exploited. Trunks of mahogany and logwood are sent to the lumber mills and the dye factories. Deforestation, one of the essential causes of Haiti’s impoverishment, is inexorably pursued.”¹⁰³ Just as this connection manifests in vicious circles, the inverse could also be true – that is, our ecology is our vital force, and would be able to sustain our economy if it were used sustainably, not as a mere “resource” but rather as a “source of life” with repercussions on the economy, the political sphere, the social realm, and so on.¹⁰⁴

Ecological liberation theologian Daniel Castillo’s is therefore correct when he states that “It would be wrong to separate the socio-economic emergency from that of the ecological, as if one exists independent of the other. To make this separation would be to extend an error endemic in the modernist worldview of conceptually dividing nature from the realm of human life (be it ‘society,’ ‘history,’ or ‘culture’).”¹⁰⁵ Haitian economy and ecology are interdependent. We have to start to understand the interconnections on which Haiti’s wealth depends; economic progress through the tourism sector, for example, is inseparable from the natural resources that constitute its “Caribbean beauty.”

¹⁰³ Frère Francklin, Edouard de Pazzis. *Paysan de Dieu: la longue route du peuple haïtien* (Paris : Bayard-Centurion, 1997), 66 : “Pour instiller un peu de force vitale a une économie anémique, la forêt est exploitée à outrance. Les troncs d’acajou et de bois de campêche prennent le chemin des scieries et des usines de teinture. *La déforestation, une des causes essentielles de la paupérisation d’Haïti*, se poursuivent inexorablement.”

¹⁰⁴ Before seeing the Earth as a *mere* “resource” to be exploited, it is noble to see her first and foremost as a “source” of life for many human and non-human, living and non-living entities. See also: Heather Eaton. “An Earth-Centric Theological Framing for Planetary Solidarity”, 23-24: “This is a significant conceptual shortcoming in promoting the image of the earth as our home without any ecological or evolutionary literacy. Earth is our source, origin, and basis for everything that makes and keeps us alive.”

¹⁰⁵ See Daniel P. Castillo. *An Ecological Theology of Liberation: Salvation and Political Ecology* (Maryknoll, New York: Orbis Books, 2019), Introduction and Chapter 1.

If Haiti is extremely poor now, Haitians have to creatively address the issue at hand knowing that, “There is a strong link between poverty and environmental degradation, which makes poor people more vulnerable to climate-change related disasters.”¹⁰⁶ In order to tackle the problems, daughters and sons of Haiti have to consider both internal factors (i.e., the poverty itself) as well as external factors (i.e., the impoverishment of the country by the global economy and the IMF). Ultimately, though, we need to learn to see the sacred essence of all things, both within and outside, by recovering a spirituality that is conducive to that. The superior of the Jesuits in Haiti, Jean-Denis Saint-Felix, shows how this spirituality would manifest in social and cultural terms:

We have to change the narrative about Haiti – on our part, but also on the media’s part, for it’s too interested in what’s not working. [Why? We do not have the response.] I’d like to see the spotlight on something else besides the problems and somewhere else than Port-au-Prince. Talk about the people, the talent. There’s too much talk about the ugliness, we don’t speak *enough* about the beauty of this country. We constantly point out the help which the country needs. However, we don’t emphasize *enough* how this country contributed to making humanity a much more livable place when it comes to rights and freedoms, struggles, solidarity, poetry and literature. We are making an effort in this respect: through our teaching, we are trying to show young people the positive aspects of the country so that it becomes a way of life, so that they become aware of the richness of their country.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁶ William Holden, et al., *Ecological Liberation Theology*, 8: Like in the Philippines, in Haiti both “Poverty and environmental degradation combined puts the poor at greater risk than better off people, by making them more vulnerable to experiencing the direct impact of disasters when climate change related calamities happen to occur.”

¹⁰⁷ Jean-Denis Saint-Félix, SJ. « Haiti, ten years after the earthquake ». The italics are mine.

CHAPTER THREE: Reception of the Integral Ecology and its Implication for Haiti

This third and final chapter deals with the reception of the Papal Encyclical Letter's concept of integral ecology in the Haitian context and its implications. The chapter concludes with a response to the basic Papal invitation of strengthening the conviction that together with all the created entities we are one single human family,¹⁰⁸ and that we should strive for a world that reflects this important notion.¹⁰⁹

Pope Francis's idea of integral ecology has been received with enthusiasm within the Church at large as well as outside of the Church, most notably among the scientific community.¹¹⁰ However, for various reasons some others, even within the Roman Catholic Church have been critical of the Encyclical, for various reasons. In Haiti, *Laudato Si'* is not widely known at the local level of the Church, but its spirit is present in both the documents of the Haitian Conference of Bishops and the Haitian Conference of Religious Women and Men whose fellow members are great witnesses to the pains of the Haitian people.¹¹¹ There have also

¹⁰⁸ LS 52.

¹⁰⁹ LS 13: "The urgent challenge to protect our common home includes a concern to bring the whole human family together to seek a sustainable and integral development, for we know that things can change. The Creator does not abandon us; he never forsakes his loving plan or repents of having created us. Humanity still has the ability to work together in building our common home." See also the original version of the poem on the environment: Jean Bertin ST LOUIS. "L'Environnement." *Les Dossiers d'Aquitaine* de Bordeaux, 2012. Also available online at https://www.bonjourpoesie.fr/vospoemes/Poemes/jean_bertin_st_louis/l'environnement (accessed 01 May 2022).

¹¹⁰ Revol Fabien (ed.). *La Réception de l'Encyclique Laudato Si' dans la Militance Ecologiste* (Paris: les Éditions du Cerf, 2015), xx. See: Fabien Revol. "L'encyclique *Laudato Si'* du Pape François (18/06/2015)", *Droit, Santé et Société*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2016, 46-51. See also : Pierre Brugidou. "La Réception de l'Encyclique Laudato Si'. Pour une Église renouvelée de l'intérieur et un monde repensé pour demain", <https://ev34.fr/Pierre-Brugidou-reception-Laudato-si-en-4-pages.pdf>, (accessed July 7th, 2022).

¹¹¹ The religious women and men are great witnesses of the pains of the Haitian people. In October 2019, through a letter addressed to His Excellence President Jovenel Moïse, they stated that they have intervened in all areas of the life of the people and the most remote and difficult places of the country. "We are the privileged witnesses of the misery of our people. Unfortunately, His Excellence seem to ignore this misery » See: Héloïse de Neuville. "Haïti, les religieux catholiques se joignent aux manifestations", <https://www.la-croix.com/Religion/Catholicisme/Monde/Haiti-religieux-catholiques-joignent-manifestations-2019-10-23-12010561> 24 (accessed May 1st, 2022).

been some efforts by Church leaders to acquaint the people of God with the encyclical. Mostly, efforts have focused on cultivating a greater awareness of the issues the Encyclical raises, and on applying the vision of integral ecology; regardless, whether the papal encyclical is explicitly discussed. In what follows, I share three examples, from the fields of spirituality, theology, and social ministry.

3.1. Spirituality for integral ecology in Haiti: In order to respond to the spiritual needs of those who live in Haiti before, during and after the *Goudougoudou*, Manresa, the Jesuit Spirituality Center located in Tabarre (a suburban area close the metropolitan region of Port-au-Prince), is a place of silence open to those who desire to have a personal experience with otherness (of God, and of the others in God’s creation) and self through prayers and discernment. With partners from other religious communities, the Jesuits of the Spirituality Center are committed to respond to the spiritual needs of many, particularly those experiencing difficulties during the aftermath of the 2010 and 2021 earthquakes; periods of time marked by recurrent political struggle, economic hardship and sanitary crises.¹¹² In order to address the *ecological* aspects of these crises, Manresa, The Jesuit Spirituality Center offers an interesting program of spiritual renewal through Eco-Ignatian retreats, ranging from days of recollection to 30-day retreats, and including day-long eco-retreats as well as workshops on ecology.¹¹³

¹¹² I want to mention that because of the earth quacks many Haitians see nature as an “enemy” within a fear-dominated worldview. See Alex K. Rayson and S Susan Deborah. “Ecophobia, Reverential Eco-Fear, and Indigenous Worldviews.” *Interdisciplinary studies in literature and environment* 26, no. 2 (2019): 422–429.

¹¹³ Meditations based on the body and the senses (not only on reflections and the minds) is part of what The Jesuit Spiritual Center’s work in Haiti. Manresa is not alone in doing such a great work. Besides the Spirituality Center, many other institutions within and outside of the Church strive to effectively respond to these needs, whether through new initiatives or through improved and re-designed programs that take into account the lessons learned along the way. For example, the Maison Verte (on the biodiversity of the sea in its fifth edition of the Cinecolo-Haiti film festival in June 2020) and Unibank (with its collection of Haiti’s variety of the fauna and the flora ecosystems), among many other institutions, are vivid examples of human investment for the cause of ecology of Haiti. None of

3.2. Theology for integral ecology in Haiti: Godefroy Midy is a Haitian Jesuit who has played a key role in the renewal of the Church and religious life since Vatican II. He holds doctorates in both philosophy and theology. His dissertation for the latter degree, which he completed at the University of Montreal in 1977, was perhaps the first sustained application of the insights of liberation theology to the Haitian context. Later, Fr. Midy taught these ideas at the major seminary in Port-au-Prince, while pastorally accompanying both female religious congregations and ecclesial base communities. Fr. Midy is also the author of many liturgical hymns in Haitian Creole.

In the middle of the upheaval of recent decades, Fr. Midy continues to produce relevant research. In his recent writings, the environmental dimension is increasingly present and in ways that can only be described as integral ecology. For example, in the collection of Midy's articles published as *Spiritualité en temps de crise*,¹¹⁴ he sketches out a "theology of life" for Haiti, where "life itself is under threat." In explaining what he means by this, he shows how the country's many "fragilities" – socioeconomic, environmental, and even historical – are interconnected. He then shows how this fragility paradoxically serves as a "trampoline" for the Haitian people to search for the deepest sources of life. While his theological writings are deeply immersed in Ignatian spirituality and rooted in his Haitian identity and experience, Midy is also notably influenced by Leonardo Boff's integration of ecology within Latin American liberation

them is affiliated with the Church. This is proof that any of us, from wherever we are positioned, can address the ecological degradation of Haiti and of the world in ways that are both effective and efficient.

¹¹⁴ Godefroy Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise*, 45: "The life-giving spirituality which aims to be integral long for the articulation of all the aspects of life to make them live as a whole in the Spirit of the Father and the Son in the service of God, of humanity and of Creation."

theology, “We must therefore read the totality of reality in terms of relation. Everything is relation. Apart from [the] relation, there is nothing.”¹¹⁵

3.3. Social Ministry for Integral Ecology in Haiti. Among the Catholic religious congregations founded in Haiti, at least two of them are largely dedicated to promoting integral ecology: the Petits Frères et Sœurs de Sainte Thérèse and the Petits Frères et Sœurs de l’Incarnation. The charism of both is to accompany rural communities.¹¹⁶ Their accompaniment includes the promotion of agroecology and other sustainable development initiatives. For example, in a rural community near Carice, in Northeast Haiti, the Petits Frères de Sainte Thérèse are working with beekeepers to reforest the area with a biodiverse mix of local species so that the bees can find plenty of flowers year-round, which will also help people’s livelihoods. Additionally, the Petits Frères et Soeurs de l’Incarnation are building artificial lakes so-called *lacs collinaires* that help for irrigation purposes in time of drought as well as for pisciculture.¹¹⁷

Of course, the Catholic Church is not the only actor working towards integral ecology in Haiti. Indeed, Catholic actors partner with others in the care for our common home. As the Jesuits have stated, “Collaboration with others is the only way the Society of Jesus [i.e., The Jesuits] can fulfill the mission entrusted to her. This partnership in mission includes those with whom we share Christian faith, those who belong to different religions such as Protestantism and Vodou, and women and men of good will, who, like us, desire to collaborate with Christ’s

¹¹⁵ Godefroy Midy. *Spiritualité en temps de crise*, 40 : “Il nous faut donc lire la totalité de la réalité en termes de relation. Tout est relation. En dehors de la relation, il n’y a rien.”

¹¹⁶ On the latter congregation’s founder, see sections of the already cited book: Frère Francklin and Edouard de Pazzis (eds.), *Paysan de Dieu: la longue route du peuple haïtien* (Paris: Bayard-Centurion, 1997), 15-40. Chapter I : Paysan avec les paysans.

¹¹⁷ Frère Francklin and Edouard de Pazzis (eds.), *Paysan de Dieu: la longue route du peuple haïtien* (Paris: Bayard-Centurion, 1997), 133.

reconciling work.”¹¹⁸ Thus, for example, the *Service Jésuite aux Migrants/Solidarite Fwontalye* – which is an international Catholic organization with a mission to accompany, serve, and defend or advocate on behalf of migrants and other forcibly displaced persons – works with public schools in Haiti to involve children in reforestation efforts, as a way of building a culture of integral ecology from the grassroots, and by giving protagonism to the newer generations.

Certainly, there is more work to be done, and deeper reflection on *Laudato Si'* would be beneficial in making those efforts fruitful, most notably the way we address our recurrent socio-environmental crises as Haitians. However, it is obvious that many actors in the Haitian Churches have understood the spirit of *Laudato Si'* and are especially attuned to the invitation and/or call to embrace the proposal of integral ecology. Indeed, many of the examples cited here precede the encyclical, even as they have been reinvigorated by it.

¹¹⁸ General Congregation of the Society of Jesus, 35.

CONCLUSION

I have shown how integral ecology, as understood in *Laudato Si'*, is a way of approaching the environment and the society that helps us to see how everything is interconnected. Indeed, “The concept of integral ecology commits us to [realizing] that climate change is connected to economics, healthcare, migration, food supplies and politics. Ecology, therefore, is not an external add-on with dimensions of life, but is, rather, intrinsic to the whole of life.”¹¹⁹ Through integral ecology, we are called to integrate an ecological vision in all of our relationships – with God, with other people, with non-human Creation, and with ourselves. For Pope Francis, this is best realized when we concentrate on our relationship with God as our Creator, which places us gratefully at the service of, and in solidarity with, our fellow creatures.

Further, I have argued that integral ecology is pertinent for the Haitian context. Because our ecological problems are so intertwined with all the rest of our problems, its approach is useful analytically, but also as a relatively neutral entry point for debates about Haiti’s overall reality on which Haitians are otherwise divided in terms of political, class, or religious identities. It is also a wise approach in its focus on relationships as the key arena for finding solutions, as opposed to a technocratic mindset, which fits well with the Haitian ethos and culture.

Finally, I have shown how the spirit of *Laudato Si'* has been taken up by ecclesial actors in Haiti. This is done in a style that echoes the concept of integral ecology very strongly, even if the encyclical itself is often not so explicitly discussed. Through spirituality, theology, and social ministry, among other areas of mission, Church leaders are promoting the vision of Pope Francis. This includes the way that many of them are doing it in partnership with others.

¹¹⁹ Dermot Lane, et al., *Theology and Ecology in Dialogue*, 24.

Despite the relevance of the ideas and the hard work of so many people, though, the environmental crisis rages on, both in Haiti and at the planetary scale. Biodiversity loss, global warming, pollution, and deforestation are all problems that require massive collective action which has not yet materialized. As in the Legend of the Hummingbird, the chaos is immense and the solutions we are able to propose feel as miniscule as what can be carried in the beak of a tiny bird. We – as daughters and sons of the Earth (as a whole) and of Haiti (as a challenging part of the whole) – can perhaps take heart in the incompleteness of the legend. What happens after the hummingbird’s interaction with the armadillo? Do the other animals keep anxiously running around in circles, or do they finally realize that if they all do their part, their burning forest can be saved? The open-ended legend does not answer these questions; it leaves that task to us.

There is, it seems to me and to many others, no single way or response that can fully address the ecological crisis; the response must be plural and multidimensional.¹²⁰ As for the line of research undertaken here, we can name some next steps that would be helpful. One important task is to continue the work of bringing the lens of integral ecology to bear on all aspects of theology, whether it is dogmatic, biblical, spiritual, or any other dimension of theology. This will surely help us to notice many new interconnections, and, also, a deeper sense of unity, between ourselves, the world around us, and the One in whom “we live and move and have our being” (Acts 17: 28 NABRE). It will also be important to bring our theological reflections about integral ecology into greater dialogue with other disciplines, such as political ecology without neglecting the humanities and the natural sciences. All these disciplines are and remain interconnected.

¹²⁰ Heather Eaton. “Working With The Climate Scientists,” Conradie Ernst M. and Hilda P. Koster. *T&T Clark Handbook of Christian Theology and Climate Change*. Edited by Ernst M. Conradie and Hilda P. Koster (London, UK: Bloomsbury Publishing, 2020), 26: Like other disciplines, “[Eco-]Theology may need to translate the [eco-]religious impulses, [eco-]spiritual sensibilities and [eco-]theological insights to be part of a larger global effort to address the causes and the consequences of climate changes of the present and to prepare for a viable future. It is the call of our times.”

Academic work in these areas should also be translated into a renewed catechesis for the grassroots Church around the world, and especially for the younger generations. Many people, including the Jesuits in Haiti, have begun revitalizing Christian spirituality through integral ecology, but we would certainly benefit from much more intentional cultivation of this mysticism which is at once new and old. And of course, like the hummingbird, the Church needs to lead by example. As St. Ignatius of Loyola puts it in the *Spiritual Exercises*, “love is expressed more in actions than in words.”¹²¹ From top to bottom, we (as both citizens of our own countries and of the world) must continue doing our part and praying for the grace of an authentic ecological conversion that leads to communication between all created entities and frank dialogue between every man of the planet, since the destinies of all countries — both the developed and the developing ones — and those of their respective ecosystems are so closely interconnected on the global scene.¹²²

¹²¹ Saint Ignatius. *Spiritual Exercises*, 230-237.

¹²² I refer here to what Pope Francis says in his third Encyclical Letter with regards to the world’s ecosystems. See: Pope Francis. *Fratelli Tutti*, 259.

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